

Robotics Research Lab
Department of Computer Science
University of Kaiserslautern

Master Thesis

RGB Camera Image

+

Radar Sensor Data Points

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Object Detected

RADAR+RGB Fusion for Robust Object Detection in Autonomous Vehicles

Ritu Yadav

March 04, 2020

Master Thesis

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Autonomous Vehicles**

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Hereby I declare that I have self-dependently composed the Master Thesis at hand. The sources and additives used have been marked in the text and are exhaustively given in the bibliography.

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(Ritu Yadav)

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Abstract

Object detection is a well-known computer vision problem and has been researched and applied in various application domains such as health care, surveillance, machine inspection, and many others. This work explores the task of object detection specific to autonomous vehicles. It describes the problems of camera-based object detection in autonomous vehicles and how other modalities can be beneficial in fixing them. Radar sensor data and RGB camera images are fused in a memory-efficient way to design multi-model object detection networks. Two variations of architecture are proposed, called RANet and BIRANet. Both networks perform fusion techniques on RGB camera images and radar sensor data to develop a robust detection network that works efficiently, even in unsteady lighting, harsh weather conditions such as rain, sun flare, fog, and others. The motivation and reasoning behind the proposed architecture are explained and compared with the recent work in this field. Proposed architectures are assessed on real-life data recorded in versatile autonomous driving conditions, which cover a wide variety of weather, crowd, traffic, and lighting scenarios in different countries. Experiments on several types of fusion, attention, and deep experts are conducted, and the performance of the introduced architecture is analyzed.

Contents

1	Introduction	2
1.1	Motivation	3
1.2	Tasks	4
2	Background	6
2.1	Two-Stage Object Detectors	7
2.1.1	Feature Extractor	8
2.1.2	Region Proposal Network	10
2.1.3	ROI Pooling Layer	13
2.1.4	Non-maximum suppression	14
2.1.5	Batch Normalization	14
2.2	Depthwise Separable Convolution Layer	15
2.3	Attention Techniques	17
2.4	General Fusion Operations	19
2.5	Level Based Fusion	20
2.6	Intersection Over Union(IOU)	21
2.7	Evaluation Metrics	21
2.7.1	Mean Average Precision and Mean Average Recall	21
2.7.2	COCO Evaluation Metrics	23
3	Related work	26
4	Approach and Implementation	29
4.1	Dataset	29
4.1.1	NuScenes Dataset	29
4.1.2	RRLAB Dataset	34
4.1.3	Data Augmentation	34
4.2	Baseline architecture	37
4.2.1	Feature pyramid network(FPN)	37
4.2.2	Loss Calculation	39
4.3	Fusion Schemes	41
4.3.1	Decision level fusion	41
4.3.2	Data level Fusion	42
4.3.3	Feature Level Fusion	42
4.4	Proposed Fused Object Detectors: BIRANet & RANet	44
4.4.1	Radar Perspective Transformation	44
4.4.2	Radar + RGB Feature Map Fusion	44
4.4.3	Attentive FPN	45
4.4.4	Radar Point-Based Anchors	47
4.4.5	RoIAlign Layer	48
4.4.6	Best of Two - RPN Target Generation Method	49
4.4.7	Loss Calculation	51
4.4.8	Non-maximum suppression	52
4.5	Training	52
4.5.1	Training parameters	52
4.5.2	Training Steps	53

	4.5.3	Evaluation Metrics	53
5		Experiments and Results	55
	5.1	Evaluation on NuScenes Dataset	55
	5.1.1	Single-Level Feature Fusion	55
	5.1.2	Multi-Level Feature Fusion	58
	5.1.3	Custom Attention	61
	5.1.4	Mixed Fusion Operation	61
	5.1.5	Feature Extractor	63
	5.1.6	Loss Hyperparameters	63
	5.1.7	Depthwise Separable Convolution	64
	5.1.8	Best Performing Configuration	65
	5.1.9	Evaluation on High and Low-Resolution Images	65
	5.1.10	Performance comparison of Proposed Network with FFPN	68
	5.1.11	Evaluate Robustness against Noise	70
	5.1.12	Evaluation on Radar Sensed Objects	76
	5.2	Inference Time	78
	5.3	Inference on RRLab dataset	78
	5.4	Result Summarization	80
	5.5	Comparison with existing Radar Fusion Methods	81
	5.6	Detection failure	82
6		Conclusion	86
	6.1	Discussion and summary	86
	6.2	Future Work	87

Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CNN	Convolution Neural Network
DL	Deep Learning
FCN	Fully Convolutional Networks
FFPN	Single shot multibox detector
FPN	Feature Pyramid Network
ML	Machine Learning
RPN	Region Proposal Network
SOTA	State-of-the-Art
VGG	Visual Geometry Group

1 Introduction

Development in arising markets, the accelerated rise of the latest technologies, and evolving consumer preferences around the world have revolutionized the automotive industries. Autonomous driving has been the focus area of the automotive industry for quite some time. This revolution is happening on both hardware and software side of the technology. Daily enhancement in the manufacturing processes, design innovations, agile development, miniaturization of hardware, and safety control algorithms are giving a direction to the current State-of-the-Art (SOTA) technology towards making our everyday lives routine less effortless. Industries and other research organizations are competing with each other to develop SOTA technology for different application areas. Frequent researches are being released and new challenges are being launched in various domain.

Research and development in the field of autonomous driving vehicles are growing intensively. Autonomous vehicles are being tested around the world by multiple groups of profound researchers and organizations. An autonomous vehicle can be defined as a vehicle that utilizes a mixture of sensors and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to drive toward a destination without a human operator. Experts define the evolution of autonomous driving in five levels. Each level describes the degree to which a car takes over its driver's responsibilities, perform required tasks on its own, and manage interaction with its driver. Defined five levels are; 1) Driver assistance, 2) Partly automated driving, 3) Highly automated driving, 4) Fully automated driving, 5) Full automation. In recent years, similar interest has been manifested by governments, industry, and research institutes where vast amounts of money and human effort are being poured in to stretch the limits of this field. Google, Tesla, Uber, Bosch, Daimler, Audi, BMW are few of the big names which are experimenting and launching autonomous driving features in their new models incrementally. These companies are either developing or have already developed vehicles having features from function-specific automation such as parking assist, lane assist to high level self-driving feature automation. Autonomous cars are being tested in every-day-driving situations with traffic rules, blocked routes, static and dynamic hurdles, obstacles, and many other real-world complex scenarios.

Autonomous vehicles are enjoying so much attention due to the increased benefits that vehicular autonomy brings along with itself. As we know, humans have limited capacity to fasten the speed of processing information, which is the reason behind most of the accidents. However, at the same time, humans are experienced in a wide range of scenarios and can stimulate new possible real-life situations on their own. Computers, on the other hand, are highly efficient in computation but are not aware of all kinds of situations that can occur in real-life scenarios. Autonomous vehicles, if equipped with efficient computing mechanisms along with many inexpensive and rich sensors, can observe its environment as humans do, can get combined advantages, and can perform better than humans.

Technological developments towards autonomous driving boost the attractiveness of the car: car driving gets even simpler, less time consuming, and more carefree. These developments are incredibly desirable to car drivers and are, therefore, urged immensely by car-driving customers. The demand for autonomous driving can be attributed primarily to the fact that it decreases accidents and air pollution in urban areas by more reliable driving and efficient fuel usage. It contributes to controlled traffic and diminishes parking problems. Further to this, autonomous vehicles not only speed up life by quick transportation of goods but also

increase safety by reducing human error. Another reason why this technology has been lately evolving worldwide is primarily due to the recent success of Deep Learning (DL) and Machine Learning (ML) methods in computer vision. DL has made a tremendous impact on computer vision, reaching previously unattainable performance on tasks such as image classification, object localization, object detection, object tracking, image segmentation, pose estimation, image captioning and others. The progress, demands, and expectations of DL are undoubtedly symbols of the Big Data era, where images of any sort and computable capabilities are more accessible than ever before.

In this work, one specific domain of this technology is addressed, which concentrates on object detection problems and their solutions in autonomous driving scenarios. Various methods are explored by which object detection networks can be made more robust towards various outdoor conditions by fusing radar sensor data with computer vision-based deep convolutional neural networks.

1.1 Motivation

With increasing demand and research in autonomous vehicles, object detection has become a significant task. RGB camera images are the standard input of traditional object detectors. However, adverse weather conditions or dark environment conditions distort the images or videos captured by a camera as shown in Figure 1. Unpredictable environmental conditions make it troublesome for single modality based object detectors to detect the object's location, and its category precisely.

Figure 1: Distorted image examples under different lighting and weather conditions.[Caesar 19]

To overcome this limitation, vehicle industries are using different sensors in autonomous vehicles such as LIDAR, radar, infrared cameras, and others. Each sensor has its benefits and drawbacks. LIDAR and radar sensors have most commonly come into the picture when analyzed on the basis of usability. LIDAR sensors are highly efficient in reconstructing 3d images of objects but at the cost of the reliability issue. LIDAR has more moving parts hence have room for more noise. Radar sensors, on the other hand, provide very few points hence are not suitable for 3d object image construction. However, radar sensors have a high range, due to which they can detect objects at a long distance. They are robust, reliable, and cheaper than LIDAR sensors. Long-range object detection is beneficial for autonomous vehicles, especially for commercial vehicles such as trucks, where they need more time to slow down for an incoming obstacle or object. Radar sensors and RGB cameras, make a very reliable combination for object detection. Even after these significant merits of radar sensors, there are limited significant research works conducted on radar

sensor and vision fusion. Presented work explores these two sensors and analyze their benefits in the task of object detection for autonomous vehicles.

1.2 Tasks

In this work, an architecture for object detection is introduced, which utilize RGB camera images and radar sensor data. Radar sensor provide points which store high confidence information about location of objects and their distance from the sensor. Along with other intuitive work, high confidence radar sensor information is used for better feature extraction and region proposals. Proposed approaches are implemented to build a robust object detection network for the autonomous driving environment.

Basic tasks of this work are:

- Preprocessing on radar sensor and camera data.
- Fuse Radar signal data and RGB camera images in a pipeline for object detection.
- Find the most efficient architecture for the fused object detection.
- Evaluate models for object detection performance.
- Evaluate models for robustness towards noise.
- Comparison with existing similar works.

2 Background

This chapter covers topics that will help in understanding the approach and methodology used in the proposed work.

Object detection is a computer vision technique to identify what objects are in the image or video and locate them. Detected objects are usually marked in rectangular bounding boxes, as shown in Figure 2. The object Detection technique is further extended to object tracking, instance segmentation, segmentation, and others. Object detectors identify objects in an image or video on the grounds of their spatial and contextual features, just like a child identifies objects in real life by recognizing certain features of them.

Figure 2: Object Detection Example.

Object detection techniques are typically divided into ML based approach and DL approaches. ML approaches focus on defining features by using traditional methods such as haar like features [Neumann 17], Scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) [Lindeberg 12], Histogram of oriented gradients (HOG) [Neumann 17] and others. After detecting features, they are classified using classification techniques such as support vector machines (SVM) [Liu 05]. However, DL techniques develop end to end object detectors based on convolutional neural networks(CNN).

With the introduction of CNN, informative representation of objects is learned, and it shows drastic improvement in tasks such as classification and regression. CNN based object detectors are very efficient and common these days. DL based object detectors are generally divided into two categories named as two-stage and single-stage object detectors. On the one hand, we have two-stage detectors, such as Faster R-CNN (Region-based Convolutional Neural Networks) [Ren 15] or Mask R-CNN [He 17], with (i) the first stage where regions of interest are generated using a Region Proposal Network (RPN) and (ii) the second stage where the generated region proposals from RPN are pushed into the object classification and bounding-box regression pipeline. On the other hand, we have single-stage detectors such as SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector) [Lin 17b] and YOLO (You Only Look Once) [Redmon 16], that handle object detection as one stage regression task. It takes an input image and learn the class probabilities and bounding box coordinates of the objects. Two-stage models perform better in terms of accuracy but are typically slower in inference.

This work presents object detection networks by fusing two modalities radar sensors and RGB camera image. In order to explore the fusion at multiple stages of the network we choose Two-stage object detectors for the presented work.

2.1 Two-Stage Object Detectors

Faster R-CNN is the first two-stage object detector introduced, and R-CNN [Girshick 14] is the first step to Faster R-CNN. R-CNN, shown in Figure 3 uses search selective algorithms to find out the regions of interest and passes them to a convolution network. It tries to combine areas where similar pixels and textures are present in the input image in order to find possible objects. The selective search approach is used to propose 2000 rectangular bounding boxes per image, which are passed through a pre-trained CNN. The output feature map from this CNN is then passed through SVM for classification and regressor for bounding box predictions.

Figure 3: R-CNN. Network (1) takes an input image, (2) extracts around 2000 bottom-up region proposals, (3) computes features for each proposal using a large convolutional neural network (CNN), and then (4) classifies each region using class-specific linear SVMs [Girshick 14]

Figure 4: Fast R-CNN architecture. An input image and multiple regions of interest (RoIs) are input into a fully convolutional network. Each RoI is pooled into a fixed-size feature map and then mapped to a feature vector by fully connected layers (FCs). The network has two output vectors per RoI: softmax probabilities and per-class bounding-box regression offsets. The architecture is trained end-to-end with a multi-task loss. [Girshick 15]

Fast R-CNN [Girshick 15] takes one step forward and instead of applying CNN individually on 2,000 proposed areas, it only passes the original image through a pre-trained CNN model first (Figure 4). Then the selective search algorithm compute the proposals on the

output feature map from the previous step. Outputs of the selective search are variable sized proposals. Since the network has fully connected layer, these variable sized proposals are need to be encoded into fixed size proposals. To ensure a pre-defined fixed output size ROI pooling layer is used, which are then passed as input to a fully connected layer. At the end of the pipeline, two output vectors are used for predicting object's category and it's bounding box. A softmax classifier is used for the classification and linear regression is used to get the offset for the bounding box localization.

Faster R-CNN makes further improvement on Fast R-CNN. Similar to Fast R-CNN, Faster R-CNN also has two stages where in one stage region proposals are refined and in second stage final object classification and regression is performed on these refined proposals. But in Faster R-CNN search selective process is replaced by a subnetwork called Region Proposal Network (RPN). The architecture of Faster RCNN is shown in Figure 5. To understand the background of the presented thesis work, it is essential to understand a few concepts of two-stage detectors which are described in the following subsections.

2.1.1 Feature Extractor

A feature extractor is an algorithm or a neural network used to extract important features from the raw input. Feature extraction is a process of dimensionality reduction by which the large and raw input data is filtered into more manageable groups of features. Generally object detectors deal with large input datasets containing a huge number of variables, which requires immense number of computing resources for processing. It is highly probable that these large number of features available in the input are not necessarily important for the network's goal.

Feature extractor help in extracting important features out of immense number of input image features. By doing this, feature extractor effectively reduces the amount of data that must be processed by the rest of the network, while still accurately describing the original data set.

A feature extractor typically consist of convolution layers, activation functions such as relu and pooling layers such as max-pooling as can be seen in Figure6. Activation function are used to add non-linearity in the neural network. There are many activation function available for CNN. some of them are step function, sigmoid, tanh, relu and leaky relu. Pooling layers are used to reduce dimension of input featuremap which in turn reduce the paramerters hence computation power. Pooling layers discard a lot of features but at the same time keep the important features in the network for further processing. Generally pooling can be done in two ways, one is average pooling and the other is max pooling. Average pooling takes the average activation of certain number of surrounding features however, max-pooling keeps the maximum activation value feature among the surroundings. Max-pooling is the most commonly used pooling layer in CNN. Apart from this feature extractor also uses batch normalization layers which is explained further in detail in section 2.1.5.

Generally, the backbone feature extractor is adopted from the ImageNet[Deng 09] classification. For a long time, ImageNet was a reliable dataset to evaluate the performance of deep CNNs. Most of the networks are tested on the ImageNet dataset in order to compare it with the performance of other networks. AlexNet[Krizhevsky 12] is among those initial networks which tried to increase the depth of CNN. AlexNet was a good

Figure 5: Faster R-CNN Block Diagram.[Gao 17]

start but had a huge number of parameters; hence computation was still a problem. VGGNet [Simonyan 14] reduced this problem a bit by replacing all convolution operations from large kernels to a stack of 3x3 convolution. Most of the following deep CNN adopt VGG architecture along with various conceptual ideas to build better performing networks. GoogleNet[Szegedy 15] proposed inception blocks that expanded the width of the network. Inception blocks covered a variety of features by using different size kernels. ResNet [He 16] adopted “bottleneck” architecture with the help of residual identity connections. ResNet in-

roduced a way to build deeper neural networks with simple and efficient operations. Later, Group convolutional layers were introduced in ResNext[Xie 17] and Xception[Chollet 17] as a replacement of common convolution layers. Group convolutional layers not only contributed towards the performance of the network in terms of accuracy but also slashed the number of parameters. DenseNet [Iandola 14] and then EfficientNet [Tan 19] further reduced parameters while keeping competing accuracy.

VGG, ResNet and DenseNet are few of the networks which are widely used as feature extractor in object detection. VGG and ResNet feature extractor are shown in Figure 6 and 7 respectively.

Figure 6: VGG Feature Extractor.[Frossard 17]

2.1.2 Region Proposal Network

As the name suggests, region proposal network is used to generate bounding box proposals for possible objects present in the input image or video frame. Feature extractor provide output feature maps, which are the input to RPN. Before RPN, proposals are generated offline using computer vision techniques such as selective search. There are drawbacks to the selective search such as high computation cost and offline computation. Region proposal network resolve this issue and work in three steps, which are generating anchor boxes, classify each of these anchor boxes into the foreground and background class and learn the shape offset for anchor boxes to make a good fit for the objects.

Each point on the output feature map of the feature extractor is an anchor point. At each anchor point anchor boxes are generate. Anchor boxes are rectangular boxes, as shown in Figure 8, that are generated with different ratios and scales. For example, in Faster R-CNN 3 scales and 3 ratios are used for anchor box generation, which generates 9 anchor boxes for each point in the output feature map as represented in Figure 9. Combinations of different scales and ratios are used to cover variable-sized objects in the image. Anchor boxes are proposed on the image dimension, however feature maps extracted from the feature extractor backbone are reduced in size. To generate the anchor boxes in image dimension, a stride equal to the ratio of original image dimension and output feature map is used. Anchor boxes from each feature map are exacted and then multiplied with

Figure 8: Anchor Representation. [Gao 17]

Figure 9: Anchor generation block diagram. [Jiang 19]

convolution layers, and the network generates prediction classification scores and regression offset values. To enable learning in the neural network, it needs to have target classification and offset values corresponding to each input. Target classification values are available in annotations, and regression offsets are calculated from the ground truth bounding box values from the annotations. Target offset values are generated by comparing the anchor boxes with ground truth boxes. In the process of anchor target generation, the intersection over union (IOU) of ground truth bounding boxes with these anchor boxes are calculated. A threshold of IOU value is set to decide whether the anchor box belongs to the foreground class or background class. Now, the difference between the coordinate of foreground anchor boxes and ground truth bounding boxes is calculated, and this difference is set as the target offset, which is then learned by the convolutional regressor in the learning process of the network.

Once the network learns the classification and offset, these values are sorted by their confidence score. The offsets are applied to the anchor boxes to get the actual region of interest which are processed further. Briefly, RPN ranks region boxes (called anchors) and proposes the ones most likely containing objects. The time cost of generating region proposals is much smaller in RPN than selective search since RPN shares most of the computations with the object detection network.

Figure 10: Working example of ROI Pooling layer.[fractal 19]

2.1.3 ROI Pooling Layer

Second part of two stage architecture consists of fully connected layers that need fixed-size inputs. Since the proposals from RPN are generated using combinations of different scales and ratios, the output proposals are of variable size. ROI pooling [Girshick 15] layer bridges the gap between the RPN and the fully connected network of Faster RCNN. ROI pooling layer applies max pooling on non-uniform proposals to convert them into fixed-size feature maps. In ROI pooling layer, the number of input and output channels is same. ROI pooling layer takes two inputs, First, a feature map obtained from the feature extractor backbone and the second is ‘N’ number of region of interest from RPN. Each proposal hold five values, the first one is the index and the rest four values are the coordinates of the proposed bounding box. The four coordinates generally represent the top-left and bottom-right corner of the box.

ROI pooling takes each input ROI and corresponding portion from the input feature map and converts the feature-map portion into a fixed dimension map. The fixed dimension output of the ROI pooling neither depends on the input feature map nor on the size of the proposals, It solely rely on the parameters of the layer. Height and width of the fixed size pooled output are the hyperparameters that can be decided based on the nature of the problem.

Let’s assume a feature map of size 5x5 Figure 10a, with the ROI plotted on it. Boundaries of ROI don’t coincide with the feature map granularity, that is because ROI follows the coordinates of the input image, and the resolution of the feature map is now not same as that of the input image. To resolve the mentioned issue, the boundaries of ROI are rounded off to ensure it’s alignment with the granularity of the feature map as shown in Figure 10b. Depending on the expected output size, let’s assume ROI is divided into $m \times m$ bins. In this example, value of m is taken as 2 and ROI is divided into 2×2 bins. Notice in Figure 10c, the boundaries of bins and feature map generalities again do not align with each other. The quantization step similar to step 1 is again performed on this matrix, and

the outcome is visible in Figure 10d. Now the max-pool operation is applied on each bin separately and the final four values shown in Figure 10e in this example come out to be (0.32,0.64,0.16,0.25). Similarly, we get the final fixed mxm size matrix for all regions of interest.

2.1.4 Non-maximum suppression

It is possible to have multiple proposals for an object with a similar confidence score. This can lead to hundreds of proposal candidates which in-turn can increase the computation time without any benefit. Non-maximum suppression(NMS) [Hosang 17] is a technique to keep the high scored proposals and discard all neighboring proposals. NMS steps are explained in algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Non-maximum suppression

Input: A list of Proposal boxes B , corresponding confidence scores S and overlap threshold N .

Output: A list of filtered proposals D .

- 1 **while** B is not empty **do**
 - 2 Select the proposal with the highest confidence score, remove it from B and add it to the final proposal list D . (Initially D is empty).
 - 3 Compare the selected proposal with all the proposals and calculate it's IOU with every other proposal.
 - 4 If the IOU is greater than the threshold N , remove that proposal from B .
 - 5 **end**
-

Figure 11: Non-maximum suppression example. Red rectangles represent Region of Interest proposals [Sambasivarao 19]

2.1.5 Batch Normalization

Batch normalization [Ioffe 15] is a regularization method that usually accelerates the model training by enabling it to learn with higher learning-rates. In the training phase, a large dataset is pushed into the model in smaller training batches. Generally, the distribution of data in each batch differs from each other, which can lead the network in different learning directions, and activations in feature maps can go very high or low. This type of behavior in neural networks causes non-regularities, also known as covariate shift. Because

of the covariate shift, feature map activations adapt according to the batch input. As the output feature maps from one layer to another flow throughout the network, it affects the entire model, and this randomness in learning activations does not allow the network to converge quickly. Hence the model takes a long time for convergence. Batch normalization helps in avoiding this problem. It takes activations from an input layer and subtract the mean and divide it by standard deviation of the whole batch. This helps each layer of the model to learn the overall distribution of the input data in a stable manner. In the batch normalization process, the addition and division operation adds extra noise to actual activations from individual data, which helps the model to dodge overfitting problems. Batch normalization enables the model to learn parameters β and γ during the training phase to transform the mean and variance according to the input data.

$$y^{(k)} = \gamma^{(k)} \hat{x}^{(k)} + \beta^{(k)} \quad (1)$$

$\hat{x}^{(k)}$ is a single activation and $\gamma^{(k)}$, $\beta^{(k)}$ are parameters that scale and shift the normalized value during training.

2.2 Depthwise Separable Convolution Layer

Depthwise Separable Convolution Layers are commonly used in MobileNet[Howard 17] and Xception neural network architectures. Depthwise Separable Convolution factorize convolution into two parts, first is depthwise convolution and second is 1×1 convolution operation which is also referred as pointwise convolution. Depthwise convolution apply single filter for each input channel separately and proved to be quite efficient as compare to standard convolution. Depthwise convolution with one filter per input channel can be presented as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{G}}_{k,l,m} = \sum_{i,j} \hat{\mathbf{K}}_{i,j,m} \cdot \mathbf{F}_{k+i-1,l+j-1,m} \quad (2)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ is the depthwise convolutional kernel of size $D_K \times D_K \times M$ and the m_{th} filter in $\hat{\mathbf{K}}$ is applied to the m_{th} channel in F to produce the m_{th} channel of the filtered output feature map $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$. D_K is the spatial dimension of the kernel and M is the number of input channels

Computational cost of depthwise convolution is:

$$D_K \cdot D_K \cdot M \cdot D_F \cdot D_F \quad (3)$$

where D_F is the spatial width and height of a square input feature map.

Depthwise convolution apply kernel on each channel separately but does not merge them to get new features. To achieve this pointwise convolution operation is applied on the output of depth wise convolution. Computation cost of pointwise convolution can be represented as:

$$M \cdot N \cdot D_F \cdot D_F \quad (4)$$

where N is the number of output channels.

(a) Standard Convolution Filters.

(b) Depthwise Convolution Filters.

(c) 1×1 Convolutional Filters called Pointwise Convolution in the context of Depthwise Separable Convolution**Figure 12:** Depthwise Separable Convolution. [Howard 17]

Combination of the two operation form depthwise separable convolution and the collective computation cost is:

$$D_K \cdot D_K \cdot M \cdot D_F \cdot D_F + M \cdot N \cdot D_F \cdot D_F \quad (5)$$

However, Computation cost of standard convolution can be given as:

$$D_K \cdot D_K \cdot M \cdot N \cdot D_F \cdot D_F \quad (6)$$

On comparison, we see that if we use depthwise separable convolution instead of standard convolution we get a reduction in computation of $\frac{1}{N} + \frac{1}{D_K^2}$. Hence, depthwise separable convolution reduce the computation to a large extent while providing competitive accuracy. Visualization of the standard and depthwise seperable convolution is presented in Figure 12.

2.3 Attention Techniques

Concept of attention in neural networks is similar to how we humans pay attention to certain things or parts in a scene. Human visual attention allows us to focus on specific parts of the scenes with high resolution and look at the rest of the scenes with low resolution. Accordingly humans adjust their focal point and recognize objects by identifying certain features of objects more prominent than others in the scene. Neural networks also work on the basis of features of objects in the scenes and following the concepts of attention in humans we want our neural network to pay attention to features from certain parts of the object. Since these features where attention should be paid changes from case to case basis, attention parameters are made learnable and are learned during training.

Attention mechanisms have its application in multiple fields of deep learning such as Computer Vision, Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks and others. Attention is mainly popular in NLP tasks but also provided significantly good results in computer vision tasks.

Figure 13: Squeeze & Excitation networks [Hu 18]

Among many Squeeze & Excitation networks [Hu 18] are a kind of attention which gave significant improvement in tasks like classification and object detection. Squeeze & Excitation(SE) building block is shown in Figure13 which improved channel inter dependencies with no additional computational cost. In a normal convolution block all channels are weighted equally hence are of equal importance. Idea of SE block is to add an extra parameter(r) to each channel of the input convolution block(X) which decides

Figure 14: Squeeze & Excitation network on Residual Block [Hu 18]

their weightage. Each channel in the input convolution block of size $W \times H$ is observed spatially and squeezed to 1 weight value per channel. This results in a vector of size C , where C is equal to the number of channels in the convolution layer. Output is then pushed through an FC layer with channels equal to C/r where r is the dimensionality reduction ratio. Relu and a dimensionality increasing layer is applied to bring it back to the channel dimension i.e. $(1 \times 1 \times C)$. Each value in the vector C conceptually tell the importance of each channel in the convolution block.

Now the final output of the block is obtained by rescaling U with the activations s :

$$\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_c = \mathbf{F}_{scale}(\mathbf{u}_c, s_c) = s_c \mathbf{u}_c \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = [\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_1, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_2, \dots, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_C]$ refers to the output and $\mathbf{F}_{scale}(\mathbf{u}_c, s_c)$ represents the channel-wise multiplication between the scalar S_C and the feature map $\mathbf{u}_c \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$. The scaling operation boost or reduce the significance in the each channel of the input feature map accordingly. In this way SE blocks generates an attentive mechanism which weight each channel of the convolutional block adaptively. Example of channel-wise attention by SE block on ResNet block is shown in Figure14. Later, it was suggested that if it is possible to get the channel-wise important feature, it is possible to get the importance parameter for spatial features as well. Multiple variations of such ideas and combinations of spatial and channel-wise attention are proposed in different convolution networks.

Concurrent Spatial and Channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’(scSE) blocks [Roy 18] suggest one of such combined attention mechanisms. The scSE block is a combination of two blocks as shown in Figure15, where U refers to input, \hat{U}_{scSE} refers to the output and $\sigma(\cdot)$ indicate the sigmoid layer. First block(cSE) include spatial squeeze and channel excitation block, which is exactly the same as the SE block explained earlier. The sSE block include channel wise squeeze and spatial excitation block. This block give importance to fine

Figure 15: Concurrent Spatial and Channel Squeeze & Excitation network. [Roy 18]

Figure 16: Different Fusion Operation

grained spatial features hence adaptively boost activation of good spatial features and suppress weak or less meaningful features.

When the combination of cSE and sSE blocks are applied on input U , it re-calibrates the input both spatially and channel-wise. The Concurrent Spatial and Channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’(scSE) is obtained by adding the output excitation \hat{U}_{cSE} from cSE and \hat{U}_{sSE} from sSE block as shown in equation below.

$$\hat{U}_{scSE} = \hat{U}_{cSE} + \hat{U}_{sSE} \quad (8)$$

This re-calibration of features encourages the network to learn more meaningful feature maps, that are significant both spatially and channel-wise.

2.4 General Fusion Operations

In deep neural networks different modalities are fused typically using below mentioned operations also shown in Figure16. Let’s assume two modalities denoted by M_i and M_j , and $f_l^{M_i}$ and $f_l^{M_j}$ are corresponding feature maps in the l^{th} layer of the neural network. Also denote $G_l(\cdot)$ as a mathematical description of the feature transformation applied in layer l of the neural network.

- **Multiplication:** In this operation elements of a feature map from one modality are multiplied with elements of feature map of second modality. $f_l = G_{l-1} \left(f_{l-1}^{M_i} * f_{l-1}^{M_j} \right)$
- **Addition:** In this operation elements of a feature map from one modality are added with elements of feature map of second modality. $f_l = G_{l-1} \left(f_{l-1}^{M_i} + f_{l-1}^{M_j} \right)$

- **Concatenation:** Concatenation operation usually stack the feature maps from two modalities along their depth and then feed to convolution operation. In case of a fully connected layer, modality features are first flattened to form vectors which are then concatenated along the rows of the feature maps.
- **Ensemble:** In case of object detection tasks, ensemble operation typically gathers features from multiple modalities and uses them together to extract regions of interest. This is kind of middle level fusion.
- **Mixture of Experts:** Aforementioned fusion operations do not consider the amount of information available from different modality e.g. the fact that at night RGB camera images contain comparatively less information than LIDAR points. Operations are directly applied with the assumption that the network can learn to weight corresponding feature maps on their own. The Mixture of Experts (MoE) approach considers this problem and explicitly models the weight of a feature map. This method was first introduced in [Jacobs 91] for neural networks and further extended in [Mees 16, Valada 17, Eigen 13]. As Figure17 illustrates, the feature map of a modality is first processed by its domain-specific network called “expert”. Later, the outputs from multiple experts are averaged with the weights w^{M_i} , w^{M_j} predicted by a gating network which takes the combined features output by the expert networks as inputs h via a simple fusion operation such as concatenation:

Figure 17: Mixture of Experts fusion method. Features from individual modality expert networks are extracted and merged after passing through the gating network[Feng 20]

2.5 Level Based Fusion

Fusion can be categorized on basis of the location where they are applied in the network. On the basis of level of location fusion can be categorized in below explained three categories.

- **Early Fusion:** Early fusion methods are the techniques where the input from multiple modalities are merged at initial level and then fed into the networks. Input data from different modalities can be merged using addition, multiplication or concatenation operation.

- **Late Fusion:** Late fusion is an approach where experts of different modalities are trained separately and the outputs from these modalities are combined together. These combined outputs can be fed into another network for combined learning or they can directly be used to extract final output after applying some decision algorithm.
- **Middle Fusion:** Middle level fusion are the approaches which are used to combine data or features from different modalities at some middle level in the neural network. There are multiple ways to fuse modalities at middle level. Modalities can be fused feature wise in later layers of the network, they can be fused for region proposal networks or may be fused for applying attention or for decision making in between the network.

2.6 Intersection Over Union(IOU)

Objects in an image or video frame are detected with a bounding box around the object. This is how the ground truth is labeled and also how the convolution neural network predict the objects in the input image. Bounding boxes are nothing but x, y coordinates of the two ends of the rectangular box around object which are typically top-right and bottom-left corner coordinates. It is highly unlikely that the object detector predicts exact bounding box coordinates of an object. Hence, a metric is required to measure the accuracy of the predicted bounding box of the detected object with respect to corresponding ground truth bounding box of the object. Intersection over union(IOU) is one of the metric which is widely used for evaluation purposes in object detection task. As the name suggested IOU calculates the ratio of intersection area between the predicted and ground truth bounding box with the union of two. IOU score for two areas A and B can be given by:

$$IoU = \frac{A \cap B}{A \cup B} \quad (9)$$

In other term it can be given by:

$$IoU = \frac{TP}{TP + FN + FP} \quad (10)$$

where 'TP' represents true positive, 'FN' represents false negative and 'FP' represents false positive pixels.

IOU measure helps object detection network in learning offsets over the bounding boxes. Generally in an object detection network one or multiple IOU threshold values are fixed to decide good or bad detection. For example 0.3 IOU of predicted bounding box can be considered as a bad detection and detection with IOU greater than 0.7 can be considered as good detection as shown by example in Figure3. Depending on the available training data, requirement and other factors IOU thresholds can be adjusted.

2.7 Evaluation Metrics

2.7.1 Mean Average Precision and Mean Average Recall

The performance of an object detection network is measured on basis of combined classification and regression (localization) performance. In general the metric used for the

Table 1: Bad Detection.

Table 2: Good Detection.

Table 3: Object Detection Sample Image. Green box is the ground truth bounding box and the red box is the predicted bounding box.

performance measurement is the Mean Average Precision (mAP) and Mean Average Recall(mAR). Average precision for each class can be calculated separately under the area of the precision-recall curve.

- Precision: It is the percentage measure of correct predictions by the model.

$$Precision = \frac{TruePositive(TP)}{TruePositive(TP) + FalsePositive(FP)} \quad (11)$$

- Recall: It is the percentage measure of possible ground-truth bounding boxes being detected by the model.

$$Recall = \frac{TruePositive(TP)}{TruePositive(TP) + FalseNegative(FN)} \quad (12)$$

True Positive (TP) is the measure of predictions whose IoU with ground-truth bounding boxes is greater than a threshold value, while, False Positive (FP) is the measure of predictions having IoU less than the threshold and False Negative (FN) is the number of ground-truth bounding boxes that are not detected by the model.

First, all the prediction results are sorted by their confidence score from highest to the lowest. Then 11 different equally spaced values are chosen between range 0 and 1. These 11 values are known as rank or confidence threshold values which should be decided in a way such that recall values at those ranks are like 0, 0.1...1.0. Average precision can be calculated as the average of maximum precision values at those 11 selected recall values.

Average precision for class c is defined as:

$$AP_c = \frac{1}{11} \sum_{r \in (0, 0.1 \dots 1)} \max(P(r)) \quad (13)$$

Here $P(r)$ is the precision value for one of the 11 recall values (r)

Mean average precision is the average of AP's over all the classes. The mAP is given as:

$$mAP = \frac{1}{C} \sum_c AP_c \quad (14)$$

Here, C is the total number of classes and AP_c is the AP for particular class c .

Average recall (AR) is also used to find out and compare detection network's performance. AR can be calculated as twice the area under recall-IoU curve and mean average recall is the mean of AR across all classes.

$$mAR = \frac{1}{C} \sum_c AR_c \quad (15)$$

2.7.2 COCO Evaluation Metrics

MS COCO evaluation metric [Lin 14] is well known and widely used to evaluate object detection networks. Unlike older metric such as PASCAL VOC, COCO metric computes mean average precision over a range of IOUs which are easy to change according to the requirement of the task. COCO evaluation metric offers following measures on basis of IOU:

- $mAP^{IoU=.50:05:95}$, which is mAP averaged over 10 IoU thresholds (i.e., 0.50, 0.55, 0.60, ..., 0.95) and is the primary challenge metric.
- $mAP^{IoU=.50}$, which is a lenient metric of mAP over 0.5 threshold IOU.
- $mAP^{IoU=.75}$, which is a comparatively strict metric of mAP over 0.75 threshold IOU. This metric look for excellent object detection results.

COCO metric also offers another metric to evaluate object detection results on bases of size of ground truth object. Size of an object is decided on basis of area covered by the object in the input image or video frame. This evaluation of object detection results consider the entire range of IOU threshold starting from 0.50 to 0.95 with the fixed interval of 0.05.

- mAP^{small} , which is mAP cover small objects with area from 0 to 32x32.
- mAP^{medium} , which is mAP cover small objects with area from 32x32 to 96x96.
- mAP^{large} , which is mAP cover small objects with area greater than 96x96.

Similar to mAP, mAR based evaluation is also offered by COCO evaluation metric with multiple variations. mAR of the detection results can be measured on basis of number of objects per image which is fixed on basis of the requirement. However three generalized mAR metric offered by COCO metric are 1, 10, 100 detection per image as mentioned below.

- $mAR^{max} = 1$, which is mAR given 1 detection per image.
- $mAR^{max} = 10$, which is mAR given 10 detection per image.
- $mAR^{max} = 100$, which is mAR given 100 detection per image.

Another set of variation of mAR measurement is on basis of size of objects similar to mAP.

- mAR^{small} , which is mAP cover small objects with area from 0 to 32x32.
- mAR^{medium} , which is mAP cover small objects with area from 32x32 to 96x96.
- mAR^{large} , which is mAP cover small objects with area greater than 96x96.

Notice that all mAP and mAR of the COCO evaluation are referred as AP and AR everywhere.

3 Related work

In autonomous vehicles, radar-based object detection methods are explored in works such as [Duan 16, Kato 02, Manjunath 18], [Chavez-Garcia 12] and many others. All these works are based on traditional techniques such as Haar-like features [Neumann 17], Extended Kalman Filter(EKF) [Chavez-Garcia 12], occupancy grid map [Duan 16], and others.

With the introduction of Convolutional Neural Network(CNN), an informative representation of objects is learned, and it shows drastic improvement in tasks such as classification and regression. CNN based object detectors are very efficient and common these days. Two-stage object detectors generally overpower single-stage detectors in terms of accuracy. The main strength of the two-stage object detector is the region proposal network. Faster-RCNN [Ren 15] introduced region proposal network(RPN) where they made network to learn region proposals. In the field of object detection RPN was a tremendous success, which is further explored in multiple works such as GA-RPN [Wang 19], Iterative RPN [Gidaris 16], Cascade RPN [Vu 19], and others.

For the task of object detection in autonomous driving applications there are several vision based approaches which provide SOTA detection results. Multimodal fusion was approached to explore the alternatives for better results, cheaper cost and for many other reasons. But multi-sensor fusion is a challenging task. One of the early multi-sensor fusion based work was presented by Kawasaki et al. [Kawasaki 04], where they addressed the problem of high numbers of sensor combinations. They proposed a solution to the problem by introducing a general modular sensor fusion architecture based on Bayesian Network, which performs dynamic fusion. A drawback of this network was the need of BN for calculation performance. In [Bombini 06], radar data is used to find the region of interest. Once radar locate the important areas, vision search methods are applied to remove false positives from the list of proposals. This work provides a good base idea for recent region proposal networks in neural networks. In [Wu 09], authors fused information from stereo camera and radar sensors to accurately estimate the location, pose, size and motion of a threat vehicle. They used vision and radar information separately to find the threat vehicle. Information from the two modalities are validated with each other in the fused network and then extended kalman filter(EKF) is used for object tracking.

Radar and vision fusion are also explored to help visually impaired people in works such as [Wu 09] and [Long 19]. In [Wu 09], authors presented a fused detection network which detect objects based on particle filters and Meanshift algorithm [Cheng 95]. Results of the network were stable with different illumination range and also locations of objects are detected accurately. In [Long 19], authors extended the work of [Wu 09] with Mask R-CNN [He 17] and SSD [Liu 16] object detection networks. RPN is much explored on RGB camera images and very less on radar sensor data. However, there are few works such as [Meyer 19], where authors presented a 3D object detection network for car detection using AVOD architecture on radar pointclouds and camera images. Authors in [Zhang 19a], use range-doppler spectrums from FMCW radar signals and camera images for 3D object detection and estimation. Authors in [Nabati 19], presented radar points-based anchors where radar points are considered towards the center, left, right, and bottom of the object. However, the authors did not provide any specific reason for not considering the radar point at the top of the object. The idea of radar point-based anchor generation is accommodated in the presented work with some intuitive changes.

In [Zhang 19b], the fusion is performed on raw radar sensor data and camera images using EKF. The raw data from the two modalities are associated using coordinate transformations and error bound estimations. Sensor's noisy outputs are processed by covariance matrix in order to ensure the reliable detection. This method provides reliable detection in real time but the performance is not comparable to neural network based approaches.

In [Chadwick 19], authors presented a object detection model using feature level fusion scheme on RGB camera images and radar data. Architecture presented in their work was built upon the SSD detection network and ResNet18 feature extractor. Authors experimented with element-wise operations and concatenation operations for feature level fusion. In their radar feature extractor branch they used resnet blocks and fusion is experimented at different stages in the network. A lot of details about sparse radar data projection to image plane and transformations are present in the paper but it was unclear how they prepared the radar based input for the radar feature extractor branch.

This work was further used in [John 19], where the authors proposed YOLO [Redmon 16] based detection architecture with feature level fusion scheme. In [John 19], detection for small and large size objects is performed in different branches. They proposed a network with two branches named RVNet , where the first branch detects objects based on RGB camera images and second branch detects objects using fused radar and vision network. On the basis of size of objects two variations of this network are presented where one of the branches detects small size objects and the other one detects large size objects and in the output branch the results from two branches are merged. For radar and RGB feature fusion concatenation operation is used.

In the work of [Nobis 19], the authors presented a network named as CameraRadarFusion-Net (CRF-Net) where feature level fusion is performed not only at one level but at all levels and they let the network decide where it is beneficial for the detection task. For this work they used retinanet [Lin 17b] as their base network and fusion is performed by using element-wise addition operation. Authors also introduce a training strategy called BlackIn for ensuring the model convergence in training. Fusing the radar data at all levels using specifically element-wise addition operation puts extra load on network parameter wise.

In the presented work, two variations of a fused detection network are proposed which use feature level and data level fusion methods. Also instead of using all level feature fusion and adding the burden of extra parameters, an optimized fusion configuration is presented. Radar point based anchors and attention mechanism are used further for more efficient detection results.

4 Approach and Implementation

This chapter covers the approach, methodology, and design of the architecture proposed in this work. Subsection 4.1 gives an explanation about datasets used for training and evaluating the model. Subsection 4.2 describes the architecture of the baseline method shortly, followed by an introduction to the fusion methods in subsection 4.3. The architecture of the Proposed object detection network is described in subsection 4.4, and further to this details related to the training process and evaluation metric are shared in the last subsection.

4.1 Dataset

Datasets play a vital role in the field of DL. A useful dataset gives a significant boost to an algorithm’s performance. Preparing a sizeable amount of good and standard datasets requires time and knowledge to gather relevant information. There are several publicly available standard datasets in the field of image processing. However, to our knowledge NuScenes [Caesar 19] is the only publicly available dataset that has synchronized radar sensor data with RGB images. The following sections consist of a brief description of the dataset used.

4.1.1 NuScenes Dataset

For training and evaluation, NuScenes dataset is used and few sample of the dataset are shown in Table 4. The NuScenes dataset is a large-scale public dataset for autonomous driving, which has recorded data from a full autonomous sensor suite(6 RGB cameras, 1 LIDAR, 5 RADAR, GPS, IMU) as shown in Figure 18. The full dataset include approximately 1.4M camera images, 390k LIDAR sweeps, 1.4M RADAR sweeps, and 1.4M object bounding boxes in 40k keyframes. This dataset is inspired by the KITTI dataset, and compared to KITTI, NuScenes include 7x more object annotations.

Figure 18: NuScenes Sensor Setup [Caesar 19].

Data is recorded in dense and highly crowded traffic situations in Boston and Singapore. 1000 scenes, each with a length of 20 seconds, are selected manually to keep all varieties of

Table 4: Sample images from the dataset.

traffic situations and driving behaviors. Each scene covers dozens of objects in different locations, weather conditions, vehicle types, vegetation, road markings, and left versus right-hand traffic. To our knowledge, it is the only publicly available dataset where radar data and camera images are synchronized. For object detection, NuScenes provide 3D bounding boxes with 23 classes along with various options like visibility, pose, activity, and others.

To use the NuScenes dataset for presented object detection task we did following changes

Table 5: Images with 3d ground truth Bounding boxes.

and preprocessing:

- Our object detection task is on two-dimension objects, and the ground truth annotation of NuScenes dataset is for three-dimensional objects. To fit into the requirement,

3D bounding boxes annotation as shown in Table 5 are converted into 2D bounding boxes.

- Twenty-three classes of NuScenes are merged into relevant classes to obtain six classes that are useful for the autonomous driving environment. The six classes in the output NuScenes dataset are Car, Truck, Person, Motorcycle, Bicycle, and Bus.

Figure 19: Example of 2D ground truth bounding box annotations with fully occluded 0% visible objects.

- In the dataset, there are ground truth bounding box annotations that are not visible in the image due to full occlusion, as shown in Figure 19. It is known that objects which are fully occluded can not be detected by an object detector. Since fully occluded objects are part of the ground truth annotation, this will affect the performance measurement of the object detection network. Hence, such annotations need to be excluded from the dataset.

NuScenes dataset provides an option to refine the dataset according to the percentage of visibility of the object in an image. All visibility options provided are listed in Table 6. The minimal option provided by the NuScenes dataset is to exclude objects having visibility level from 0 to 40%. We set the visibility level as greater than equal to two and exclude objects which are not at all visible or highly occluded in the scene. Results after fixing the annotation by visibility level of objects can be seen in few examples shown in Table 7.

Visibility Token	Description
1	visibility between 0 and 40%
2	visibility between 40 and 60%
3	visibility between 60 and 80%
4	visibility between 80 and 100%

Table 6: Visibility levels.

Table 7: 2D ground truth bounding boxes. On the left, visualization of images with ground truth bounding box annotation of completely occluded objects. On the right, images with removed occluded ground truth bounding boxes.

- Almost all existing object detection networks are trained and tested on the COCO dataset. In order to compare the presented network with existing ones, we needed the annotations in COCO format. So we wrote a scripts to convert the NuScenes dataset annotation into COCO annotation format.
- For training and testing purposes, the dataset is split into 80:20% respectively. Which result in 32254 training image and 5782 validation images.

4.1.2 RRLAB Dataset

RRLAB Dataset is a set of 3254 RGB camera images and corresponding radar sensor data. It is captured in university environment. Images are recorded at 480×640 resolution. Few sample of the dataset is shown below in Table 8.

Table 8: Image samples from RRLAB Dataset.

4.1.3 Data Augmentation

NuScenes dataset cover most of the scenes under different weather and lightening conditions. On addition to the environment conditions in NuScenes dataset, driving scenes can vary from slight fog or dust noise to severe reflection, speed blur and other effects. In order to evaluate the robustness of the networks proposed in upcoming section, three evaluation datasets are prepared on top of NuScenes evaluation dataset. Different level of noises are added to the evaluation images with the help of augmentation techniques. Four evaluation set along with the details of augmentations are mentioned below:

- Evaluation Set 1: This is the NuScenes evaluation set without any augmented noise on it's images.
- Evaluation Set 2: In this evaluation set, minute noise is added to each image. Noise added are average blur with kernel size 2 and additive Gaussian noise with standard deviation equal to 0.005. Added noise is not so clearly visible in small size images but effect the features of the image significantly.
- Evaluation Set 3: In this evaluation set, more blur and Gaussian noise are added to create a dusty and foggy environment. Sample of the added noise on image are shown in Table 9. In this configuration images are augmented with average blur of kernel size 3 and additive Gaussian noise using 0.05 standard deviation.

Sample Image from NuScenes Evaluation Set 2.

Sample Image from Evaluation Set 3.

Table 9: On the left, samples from NuScenes evaluation set 2, and on the right, sample images from augmented evaluation set 2 and 3.

- Evaluation Set 4: This noise configuration augment images with large amount of variable noise. Augmentation applied on this evaluation set are brightness, shadow, speed, sun flare and rain effect. Sample of these extreme noisy evaluation images are shown in Table 10 and 11.

Sample Image from Evaluation Set 4: Rain effect.

Sample Image from Evaluation Set 4: Shadow effect.

Sample Image from Evaluation Set 4: Speed effect.

Table 10: On the left, samples from NuScenes evaluation set 1, and on the right, sample images from augmented evaluation set 4.

Sample Image from Evaluation Set 4: Brightness effect.

Sample Image from Evaluation Set 4: Sun Flare effect.

Table 11: On the left, samples from NuScenes evaluation set 1, and on the right, sample images from augmented evaluation set 4.

4.2 Baseline architecture

The base network considered for the thesis work is Faster RCNN with feature pyramid network (FFPN) [Lin 17a]. FFPN is conceptually the combination of Faster R-CNN network and feature pyramid network. FFPN adds a feature pyramid network on top of feature extractor backbone to obtain better features for its region proposal network and the rest of the architecture of FFPN is same as Faster R-CNN. Faster RCNN takes a single scale input image and extract region proposals from the last feature map of feature extractor backbone. However, FFPN takes a single scale input image and extracts proposals from multiple level of feature maps. FFPN specifically uses ResNet as a feature extractor backbone.

4.2.1 Feature pyramid network (FPN)

Feature maps towards the end of the feature extractor backbone are generally rich in contextual semantic information leading to good object detection for large-size objects but are not that helpful in detecting small size objects. The feature maps obtained from the initial layer are rich in spatial information hence good to detect small size objects. In the Feature pyramid network, semantics from low to a high level are collected by extracting feature maps from multiple levels of feature extractor backbone, which helps in collecting good features for small objects as well as large objects. The process of feature pyramid network (FPN) is independent of the feature extractor backbone. FPN involves three parts,

namely a bottom-up pathway, a top-down pathway, and lateral connections, as shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Feature Pyramid Network Architecture.

The bottom-up pathway is part of the feature extractor backbone where convolution layers extract features, and after each stage, the size of the feature map is scaled by half. Since the last or deepest layer of a convolution network carry the most substantial features, it is selected to be the topmost layer of the feature pyramid network, which enriches the whole pyramid with its contextually strong feature information. Specifically, for ResNet feature maps from the last residual block of each stage are used. The output from these last residual blocks is represented as C2, C3, C4, C5 for conv2, conv3, conv4, and conv5, respectively. Selected four convolution feature maps to have strides of 4, 8, 16, 32 pixels with respect to the input image. Also, it is essential to note that the feature map from the last residual block of the first stage, which is conv1, is not used here. This is because the initial layer of any convolution network has high resolution hence large memory consumption.

In the top-down pathway, low-resolution feature maps with spatially coarser but semantically stronger features enhance the low level high-resolution feature maps. This is done with the help of a lateral connection between consecutive level feature maps. Figure 21 shows the building block that constructs our top-down feature maps. The low-resolution feature maps are spatially upsampled by a factor of two, which is equivalent to the size of one level up feature map. The upsampled feature map is then merged with corresponding bottom-up maps (which undergo a 1×1 convolutional layer to reduce channel dimensions). Merge operation is performed with the help of element-wise addition. This process is repeated for each two consecutive feature maps until the finest resolution map is generated. To start the iteration, a 1×1 convolutional layer is applied on C5 to get the coarsest resolution map. A 3×3 convolution on each merged map is appended to generate the final feature map, and this also nullifies the effect of upsampling done in previous steps. Finally, a set of feature maps named P2, P3, P4, P5, corresponding to C2, C3, C4, C5 are obtained, all of which are of the same spatial size but differ in the number of channels.

In the case of the ResNet feature extractor backbone, at every layer, feature map size is reduced by half, and the number of feature maps is doubled. From ResNet feature

extractor, four feature maps are extracted from layer-2, layer-3, layer-4, layer-5 where feature map from layer-2 is the largest, and the feature map from layer-5 is the smallest feature map. All extracted feature maps are first subjected to 1×1 convolutions to bring down the channels to fix number 256. Then each of the feature maps is upsampled and added element-wise to the lower level feature map. All output feature maps are then subjected to a 3×3 convolution layer to create final four feature maps (P2, P3, P4, P5), as shown in Figure 21.

Figure 21: ResNet FPN Block example.

4.2.2 Loss Calculation

In an object detection network, there are two output branches; One tells the class of the object to which it belongs, called classification branch, and the other one predicts the bounding box co-ordinates called the regression branch. Since there are two types of output from the network, it also calculates the two types of loss for the same, which are then used for learning purposes by the neurons of the network.

Total loss calculated is the weighted sum of the classification and regression loss. The hyperparameter λ is used to control the balance between the two losses and experimented with multiple values in order to find out the best-optimized value. The combined loss of the FFPN detection network for an image is represented by the following equation:

$$L(\{p_i\}, \{t_i\}) = \frac{1}{N_{cls}} \sum_i L_{cls}(p_i, p_i^*) + \lambda \frac{1}{N_{reg}} \sum_i p_i^* L_{reg}(t_i, t_i^*) \quad (16)$$

Here, i represents the index of an anchor and p_i is the predicted probability of the anchor i to belong to a particular class of object. Ground truth label is represented by p_i^* , to

which the predicted classification value is compared in order to decide the class of the object. The L_{cls} represents the classification loss calculated over p_i and p_i^* . Classification loss is calculated by using loss log whose graphical representation is shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Log Loss.

Vector t_i represent the 4 parameterized offset coordinates $t = (t_x, t_y, t_w, t_h)$ of the predicted bounding boxes and t_i^* represent vector corresponding to the ground truth offset coordinates $t^* = (t_x^*, t_y^*, t_w^*, t_h^*)$ for the anchor i . The two term N_{reg} and N_{cls} are used to normalize the two losses where N_{reg} is the total number of anchor locations and N_{cls} is the batch size. The hyper parameter λ is set to value 10 by default.

Regression loss is cal between the target bounding box offset tuple and predicted bounding box offset tuple. Four offset parameter coordinates of bounding box regression is calculated as shown in following equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_x &= (x - x_a) / w_a, & t_y &= (y - y_a) / h_a \\
 t_w &= \log(w / w_a), & t_h &= \log(h / h_a) \\
 t_x^* &= (x^* - x_a) / w_a, & t_y^* &= (y^* - y_a) / h_a \\
 t_w^* &= \log(w^* / w_a), & t_h^* &= \log(h^* / h_a)
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

where x, y is the coordinates of center and w, h represent the height and width of the bounding box. x, x_a, x^* are predicted bounding box, anchor box and ground truth bounding box respectively. The type of loss used is smooth L1 loss shown in Figure 23 which is the conditional combination of both L1 and L2 loss. Smooth L1 loss shown in equation 18 is robust in comparison to L1 loss and also less sensitive to outliers. For high difference values between prediction and ground truth, smooth L1 use L1 loss hence steady gradient. However, for values less than one it act as L2 loss hence less oscillations during updates.

$$L_{reg}(t, t^*) = \sum_{i \in \{x, y, w, h\}} \text{smooth}_{L1}(t_i - t_i^*) \tag{18}$$

$$\text{smooth}_{L_1}(x) = \begin{cases} 0.5x^2 & \text{if } |x| < 1 \\ |x| - 0.5 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Both classification and regression losses are calculated individually for region proposal network and faster R-CNN and the total loss is the sum of the two.

Figure 23: Graph comparison of L1, L2 and Smooth L1 Loss.

4.3 Fusion Schemes

The idea of sensor fusion is inspired by humans. Humans use multiple sensors to sense different attributes or specifications, which are refined together to come to a final observation. When it comes to artificial sensor fusion, the same approach is followed. In the proposed architecture, input from RGB cameras and radar sensors are fused, refined, and processed for object detection.

Below is the basic idea of the fusion schemes which are approached initially and approaches which are finally adopted in the presented thesis work.

4.3.1 Decision level fusion

This type of fusion method is applied at the later stage of the network and works on the decision level. For each modality, the input is processed separately through their own expert network, and the predictions from the different modality network are fused together to provide the final output detection result as shown in Figure 24. The process of getting final output prediction from the individual modalities can be done by performing multiple types of late fusion. For example, final output prediction can be the addition of the prediction output from two separate modalities. A separate algorithm can be applied to extract the best prediction results from the output of individual modalities together. Another method can be by adding a few more layers on top of the final prediction for further joint training.

Since there are different networks involved in predicting the detection from separate modalities and also different modalities involve different types of noises, it is challenging to design a joint detection probability density function, which is essential to build a fusion filter algorithm in the decision level. In practice, it is found that the performance improvement in detection results with decision level fusion is minimal and also computationally expensive. Hence, this fusion method is not used in this work.

Figure 24: Decision Level Fusion.

4.3.2 Data level Fusion

In this fusion scheme, radar point data are directly involved in fusion, and the combined, fused data is then processed through the detection network as represented in Figure 25. Radar data points can be used for extracting the region of interest. It is known that for each image, the number of radar points from the radar sensor is very few. So It is quite clear that if the region proposal is based on these radar points, then it is not going to cover all objects in the image. However, such type of fusion can significantly reduce the computation power as well as computation time and can also provide sufficiently good object detection results. We used this type of fusion scheme in the proposed methods, and details can be found in section 4.4.4.

4.3.3 Feature Level Fusion

Feature level fusion scheme is recently becoming very popular fusion method. In this method, radar points are transformed into 2d feature maps. Depth and velocity information are embedded at the pixel level in the transformed radar feature maps. Depending on the configuration, the output radar feature map can have either single-channel or multiple channels. Now, these radar feature maps can be fused with the RGB feature map in feature extraction backbone at a different level and with different architectural configurations. Along with the mentioned fusion idea, this type of fusion is further adopted and experimented with different configurations in the presented work. A simple representation of feature-level fusion can be seen in Figure 26.

Figure 25: Data Level Fusion.

Figure 26: Feature Level Fusion.

4.4 Proposed Fused Object Detectors: BIRANet & RANet

Two variations of fused two stage object detection networks are proposed in this work, named as RANet and BIRANet. Both proposed networks adapt data level as well as feature level fusion schemes. RANet and BIRANet follow the same architecture with two significant differences; First, RANet works only on radar point-based anchors. However, BIRANet not only use the radar point based anchors but also utilizes the anchors which are generated similar to that in FFPN. Second, BIRANet has a different RPN target generation method, "Best of Two", which is explained in subsection 4.4.6. Below is a detailed description of the proposed architecture.

4.4.1 Radar Perspective Transformation

Radar sensors give radar points along with distance, velocity, azimuth, and other information. Radar points information provided by radar sensors is in the 3D coordinate system (x,y,z) , as shown in Figure 27. In this 3d coordinate system, the x and y coordinate of radar points provide the 2D location of reflective objects in the view, and the third dimension z along the driving path corresponds to the distance of that object from the radar sensor.

Radar points are initially in the vehicle coordinate system. Before feeding these points into the network, radar data points are first converted from vehicle coordinates to camera-view coordinates which will align radar points with the RGB camera images. Transformation is done by applying rotation and translation matrix on radar points in vehicle coordinate as shown in the following equation:

$$X_i = I(X_r R + T) \quad (20)$$

Here, X_i and X_r represent the data in image and radar coordinate respectively whereas, T , R and I are the translation, rotation and camera intrinsic matrix.

Figure 27: Radar Data Transformation.

It is possible to have radar data points that are reflected from multiple object's surfaces and show the false location of the reflective object, and its distance from the radar sensor. Also, there are noise radar points in the data. However, such cases are refined in the data set at high level, and the left cases are few, which are compensated when combined with meaningful features from RGB camera images.

4.4.2 Radar + RGB Feature Map Fusion

In the proposed architecture, we use feature level fusion, which is explained in section 4.3. For fusion, a separate radar feature extractor branch is formed, as represented in Figure 28. Radar points are resized and then converted into a feature map of a size equivalent

to that of the input image. At each radar point location x, y of the feature map, the z distance value is embedded and assign 0 to all other locations where there is no radar point present. The resulting radar feature map is the input of radar feature extractor and has one channel.

Figure 28: Radar+RGB Feature Level Fusion. Small purple circles represents element-wise addition. Red dots in radar signal input represent radar points.

The radar feature extractor branch and RGB feature extractor branch are fused in the feature extractor backbone. The feature extractor used for RGB images is ResNet [He 16]. In the radar feature extractor branch, since we only have the values at few locations in the feature map, it is not a good idea to apply convolution over the radar feature map. Applying convolution on such sparse feature map will increase the number of parameters hence increase memory consumption as well as computation time without adding any benefit to the performance. Instead, max pool is applied on the input radar feature map to bring it down to the size equivalent to that of the RGB feature map. Then element-wise addition operation is performed on the feature maps from the radar feature extractor branch and the RGB feature extractor branch. Radar feature map is maxpooled and scaled-down four times in order to do feature-level fusion with RGB feature maps at four stages in the feature extractor backbone. While we experimented with radar and RGB data fusion at different stages of the feature extractor, the proposed configuration shown in Figure 28 proved to be the best.

4.4.3 Attentive FPN

In Feature pyramid network(FPN) of FFPN four feature map outputs, P2, P3, P4, P5 are extracted from the feature extractor backbone. Extracted feature maps are the features on which the performance of the detection network is primarily based. Hence these features have to be as good as possible. In order to get the best possible features out of radar+RGB fused network, different type of attentions at different level are experimented. With the thought that output feature maps can be boosted further with the help of attention, a different type of attention is proposed which is shown in Figure 29.

Custom Concurrent Spatial and Channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’

Concurrent Spatial and Channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’(scSE) is explained in the background section 2.3 on which the proposed custom attention block is built. In the spatial ‘Squeeze & Excitation’ branch of the scSE, the input convolution block is squeezed along the channel by using one kernel of size 1×1 . This squeezed output is then element-wise multiplied with the input convolution block.

Figure 29: Spatial branch of Custom Concurrent Spatial and Channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’ Block.

In custom attention block, changes are made in the spatial branch of scSE and channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’ is kept same. As shown in Figure 29, two more squeeze branches are added in parallel to the existing branch with 1×1 kernel. First, branch squeeze along the channel with one kernel of size 3×3 and the second branch squeeze input along the channel with one kernel of size 5×5 . The output from the three squeeze branches are merged using element-wise addition, and the resulting output is then multiplied with the input.

Proposed FPN

After experimenting the network with multiple type of attention at different location in feature extractor backbone, attentive FPN, as shown in Figure 30 is proposed, which uses Concurrent Spatial and Channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’ block.

When the activation values from the radar feature map are added to the activation of the RGB feature map, it bring focus on locations in RGB feature map corresponding to the radar point location. Radar data points tell the location, distance, and other information of the objects in the image; these radar points are used to focus on essential regions of the image with the help of attention mechanism. The scSE attention mechanism help in boosting the activation of good features spatially as well as channel-wise and suppress the weak ones. In feature extractor backbone, the attention block is applied to radar feature map obtained after applying maxpool. Since radar feature map values are present only at locations where radar points are present, and all other values are zero, adding attention block boost the activation and guide the network to focus on those radar point locations. These boosted activation help in boosting the features in areas where there are objects

Figure 30: Radar+RGB Feature level Fusion with Attention Block.

with weak vision based features hence independent of vision based features this attention method help in creating focus at objects in the image.

4.4.4 Radar Point-Based Anchors

Radar signals are reliable source of accurate object location information even if objects are far away from the sensor, hence radar sensors have long-range. When radar points are superimposed on images, although radar signals do not point to all object's in the image but incorporate most of the objects and also those in the long-range. Therefore, it is reasonable to use radar points for generating region proposals which leads to data level fusion.

It is observed that radar points are not only present towards the center of the surface of the object but also towards the top, bottom, left, and right edges of objects. This can be seen in images presented in Table 12. Thus, in a good proposal scheme, one cannot just consider the radar point at the center of the bounding box but should also consider the radar point on all four edges of the bounding box.

Figure 31: Radar point-based Anchors. From left to right, anchor boxes towards the center, right, left, bottom, and top edge center of radar point(blue dot).

Anchor boxes are generated with 3 ratios (0.5, 1.0, 2.0) at each radar point as shown in Figure 31. Anchor boxes are generated with the consideration that each radar point is at the top, down, left, right edge of the anchor box, and also at the center(TDLRC) of the anchor box. In region proposal network, radar points are mapped to each output

Table 12: Sample images from NuScenes dataset with superimposed radar signal data.

feature map of the feature pyramid network. Anchors corresponding to each radar point are extracted with different scales based on the level of the feature map. In proposed architecture, different sized objects are accounted and for each radar point, anchors with 3 ratios are formed. Each radar point is considered to be present at 5 different positions of the anchor, which adds up to 15 anchors per radar point. Since features are extracted at 5 levels of feature maps, anchors formed per radar point become five times 15 resulting in 60 anchor boxes per radar point.

4.4.5 RoIAlign Layer

In the region proposal network of FFPN, RoIPooling is used to obtain fixed-size(e.g., 7×7) feature maps from each region of interest. RoIPool, cause harsh quantization over features which creates alignment issue between the input image and extracted features. For a good

point based proposals, it is essential to have an accurate mapping of radar points in each feature map. RoIAlign [He 17] layer help in resolving the feature alignment problem.

Figure 32: Working example of ROI Align layer. [fractal 19]

Unlike RoI pooling layer, RoIAlign layer does not try to fit the input region of interest from RPN into the feature map. But, divide the ROI into specific number of bins and in each bin, it sample a certain number of points. Then bilinear interpolation is used to calculate the values at the sampled points.

For example, ROI shown in Figure 32 is not a proper fit into the featuremap. Now RoIAlign layer first divide it into four 2x2 bins A, B, C, D shown in subfigure (a). Out of each bin four points S1, S2, S3, S4 are selected using equation shown in subfigure (b). Now, for each sample point 4 nearest neighbouring integer points P, Q, R, S (subfigure (c)) on the feature map are identified, which match the resolution of the feature map. Now, bilinear interpolation is applied on these nearest points to calculate feature value at a point. Same process is repeated for each of the four points in the bin from S1 to S4 shown in subfigure (d) and this whole process is repeated for each bin. At the end max-pooling is applied on each bin to get one value per bin as shown in subfigure (e). It can be seen by the explained example that RoIAlign layer replace the harsh quantization involve in extracting 7x7 features per region of interest and ensure the alignment of features.

4.4.6 Best of Two - RPN Target Generation Method

In the RPN targets generation method of FFPN, anchors for each input image are compared to the ground truth bounding boxes, and the IOU score is calculated. Anchors, whose IOU score is greater than 0.7 are assigned with the positive label, and those with the IOU score

less than 0.3 are assigned with the negative label. Out of all positively labeled anchor boxes, 128 positive labeled anchor boxes are selected. Positively labeled anchor boxes are then compared with the ground truth bounding boxes, and the offset is calculated as shown in equation 1017 of section 4.2.2. These offset are the target for regressors in the region proposal network, which are learned by the network.

It is possible that few ground truth bounding boxes of an image do not have any corresponding positive anchor box(i.e., Anchors with $IOU > 0.7$). In such cases, the IOU scores of all anchor boxes of the image are compared with each other, and the one with maximum IOU score is assigned with a positive label.

When experimented with radar point-based anchors, it is found that radar point-based anchoring results in getting anchors with higher IOU scores. This benefit comes when there is are radar point corresponding to ground-truth objects. But, it is well known that radar sensors do not provide reflected points for all objects in the scene. Hence radar point based anchoring method do not generate anchors for objects with no corresponding radar points and without anchors there is no detection in those regions.

The Proposed “Best of two” method as outlined in Algorithm 2 helps in overcoming the limitation of radar point-based anchoring and, at the same time utilize the benefit of generating target for region proposal network with high IOU score. “Best of two” method generates all anchors as per FFPN along with radar point-based anchors and utilize them together for RPN target generation. The benefits of this strategy are as following :

- First, objects which are not detected by using radar points can now be detected by using RGB anchors similar to FFPN.
- Second, this method increases the probability of having better anchor candidates for the RPN.

Another important point is that the stated method causes a negligible overhead at training time and no increment in inference time.

Algorithm 2: Best of Two RPN target generation method.

Input: Ground-truth bounding box(gt_bbox), RGB anchors(i_anch), radar based anchors(r_anch).

Output: 128 positive target anchors.

- 1 Assign positive/negative labels to RGB anchors and radar based anchors separately.
 - 2 **for** positive label RGB anchors(P_i_anch) **do**
 - 3 **for** positive label radar anchors(P_r_anch) **do**
 - 4 **if** $IOU(P_r_anch, gt_bbox) > IOU(P_i_anch, gt_bbox)$ **then**
 - 5 $P_i_anch = P_r_anch$.
 - 6 **end**
 - 7 **end**
 - 8 **end**
 - 9 Select random 128 positive anchors.
-

4.4.7 Loss Calculation

For the loss calculation of proposed object detection network, the log classification loss is replaced by sparse categorical cross entropy loss. Another loss named anchor loss is added for better learning. Three hyperparameters are added to combine classification, regression and anchor loss. Detailed description of the loss calculation is provided below:

Classification Loss: Sparse Categorical Cross Entropy Loss

In the used dataset, there are 7 different classes, including background class. Each object in the image is labeled with one specific class label; hence there is no overlapped classification. Sparse categorical cross-entropy Loss is found to be suitable for such a scenario and can be represented by the following equation:

$$-\sum_{c=1}^M y_{o,c} \log(p_{o,c}) \quad (21)$$

This loss is built on the basis of cross-entropy loss, which can be defined for binary class or multi-classification purposes. For a multi-classification task, two variations of cross-entropy, namely, categorical cross-entropy and sparse categorical cross-entropy, are available. Categorical cross-entropy works with data containing objects which are annotated with multiple labels. However, sparse categorical cross-entropy loss works with data having mutually exclusive class labels. Since the class labels in NuScenes dataset annotations are mutually exclusive, sparse categorical cross-entropy loss is used for classification tasks in this work. Loss is multiplied with a λ hyperparameter, which is tuned at training time. This loss is calculated over all images, and then the mean is taken.

Regression Loss: Smooth L1 Loss

Regression loss is calculated in a similar fashion as done in our base network FFPN. Smooth L1 loss is applied on target offset values and the predicted offset values over the proposed region of interest per image. Loss is multiplied with a λ hyperparameter. This loss is calculated over all images, and then the mean is taken.

Anchor Loss

Anchor loss is proposed in this work in which loss is calculated on the ground truth bounding box and the predicted bounding box. This loss is separately added to directly learn on the bounding box rather than the offset values. Weightage given to this loss is less as compared to other loss, Anchor loss shows significant improvement in the learning process. The loss function used is smooth L1 loss, and the remaining calculation is similar to regression loss.

Combined Loss

Loss used for training the proposed network is the combination of 5 losses which are following:

- Regression and classification loss for region proposal network.

- Regression and classification loss for second stage detection network.
- Anchor loss calculated at the second stage of the detection network.

Combined loss is represented by equation 22 where we combined both regression and both classification loss to form single term for each.

$$L(\{p_i\}, \{t_i\}) = \lambda_1 \frac{1}{N_{cls}} \sum_i L_{cls}(p_i, p_i^*) + \lambda_2 \frac{1}{N_{reg}} \sum_i p_i^* L_{reg}(t_i, t_i^*) + \lambda_3 \frac{1}{N_{reg}} \sum_i p_i^* L_{anch}(b_i, b_i^*) \quad (22)$$

λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 are the hyperparameter for classification, regression and anchor loss respectively. L_{anch} represent the anchor loss while b_i and b_i^* represent predicted bounding box and ground truth bounding box respectively.

4.4.8 Non-maximum suppression

As explained in subsection 2.1.4, non-maximum suppression is used to attain top predictions for each class. This makes certain that only the most probable predictions are kept by the model, while the noisy ones are discarded.

4.5 Training

Deep neural networks need high computational power and training such networks on CPU would mean extensive number of hours or perhaps days spent for training purpose before one could get the network ready for inference. Accounting this factor, training is conducted on NVIDIA TITAN Pascal GPU with 12GB of internal memory and Intel Core i7-6700K CPU. Further technical specifications of GPU configurations can be found in Table 13. Implementation of this work is done on keras library built on tensorflow. It is an open source machine learning software library, which supports design, development and deployment for a wide range of ML tasks.

GPU Architecture	Pascal
Frame Buffer	12GB G5X
Memory Speed	11.4 Gbps
Boost Clock	1582 MHz

Table 13: GPU Configurations.

4.5.1 Training parameters

The experiments conducted for this work include preprocessing steps on images such as resizing images and creating train-validate split. Object detection using computer vision techniques is excellent with high resolution cameras i.e, more the network can see more it can learn hence contribute more in detection. However, these high resolution cameras are very expensive which divert the manufacturers to explore other cheaper sensors. While conducting the experiments it is kept in mind to build a multi-model object detection

network which can provide good object detection results with both low resolution and high resolution camera images.

Both BIRANet and RANet are trained on high-resolution images of size 1024×1024 as well as low-resolution images of size 512×512 . Since different resolution images are used for training and evaluation purposes, scales to extract anchors from FPN feature map should also be changed accordingly. Scales used for images of size 1024×1024 are 16, 32, 64, 128, 256 and for images of size 512×512 are 8, 16, 32, 64, 128. Maximum number of objects per image is set to 100. Batch size of 2 is used throughout the experiments for both variations of the proposed object detection networks. Networks are trained on different number of epochs depending on variation of attention block, feature extractor and level of fusions used in different experiments. BIRANet and RANet are trained on total of 700 scenes of training data and 150 scenes of validation data, which contains a total of 38036 radar-vision image pairs. Optimizer used is Stochastic Gradient Descent(SGD) with 0.9 momentum and weight decay is set to 0.0001.

4.5.2 Training Steps

Training of these networks is conducted in multiple steps; First, base network FFPN is trained on COCO dataset [Lin 14] with ResNet50 feature extractor. Then the trained weights are used to initialize layer wise weights of RANet and BIRANet. Network are further trained on the NuScenes training dataset. Step-wise training method is used for training networks throughout the experiments. First, training is conducted only for network heads which are the layers from second stage of object detection network. Second, networks are further trained upto second residual block of feature extractor. In third step entire network is trained. Different learning rates are used for training purpose, starting from learning rate(LR) of 0.001, which is scaled down to 0.0005 and then 0.0001 after training on certain number of epochs.

4.5.3 Evaluation Metrics

All experiments are evaluated using MS COCO evaluation metric as explained in section 2.7 with few addition described below. Precision and Recall is calculated with different IOU values from range 0.5 to 0.95 as explained in section 2.7. Since the presented work is based on sparse radar-point data, it is assumed to expect very fine improvements in object detection. To evaluate the object detection results on finer level, another metric of average precision is added which calculates AP over 0.85 IOU value. Mean average precision and mean average recall is calculated over complete range of IOU from 0.50 to 0.95 with interval of 0.05, also mean average recall is measured on basis of number of objects detected per image.

In computer vision detecting middle size and small size objects is a significant problem. Although medium size objects are detected with low accuracy as compare to large size objects but are still detected with good level of accuracy. However, small size object detection is a hard problem. In driving road scenario, small objects are generally pedestrian or bikers which are must to detect and avoid any collision. Also, it is important to detect objects from a far distance for heavy autonomous vehicles, so that their speed can be controlled accordingly in order to avoid any accident. Keeping mentioned factors in mind evaluation on different size objects are presented in this work.

5 Experiments and Results

In this section, all the experiments conducted for the reach the configuration of the presented work are described along with their architecture, design motivation, quantitative comparison, and qualitative comparisons. Proposed networks are evaluated on a different level of fusion, multiple types of feature extractors, convolution layers, attention methods, and feature extractors.

Networks with the best configuration are then evaluated against different image sizes and against a variety of noise. They are first evaluated on NuScenes evaluation set and then on augmented noisy evaluation sets. Results of proposed networks, RANet, and BIRANet are compared with the base network FFPN. Inference on RRLAB dataset is presented along with the comparison of detection by the three detection networks. In the proposed networks are compared with existing radar and vision fusion-based detection networks on NuScenes dataset.

5.1 Evaluation on NuScenes Dataset

Subsections from 5.1.1 to 5.1.7 contain the experiments conducted to determine the best configuration of the network. Subsection from 5.1.9 and onwards present different evaluations done on the obtained networks with the best configuration.

5.1.1 Single-Level Feature Fusion

In this set of experiments, Radar data and RGB camera images are fused at data level and feature level. In feature level fusion features from the two modalities are fused at single-level, which is at the second stage of RGB feature extractor. This set of experiments are conducted on BIRANet and input size used is 1024×1024 . Also, feature extractor used for RGB feature extraction is ResNet50.

Figure 33: Radar Feature extractor branch.

Experiment 1

Proposed object detection network is experimented with several architectural fusion differences. In this experiment, a ResNet block is applied on input Radar featuremap which is the inspiration from the work presented in [Chadwick 19]. The ResNet block applied in Radar feature extractor branch is shown in Figure 33.

Figure 34: Experiment 1: Single-level feature fusion(Radar+RGB).

The output of this ResNet block(R2) is then fused with the Second stage output of RGB feature extractor branch. The operation used for fusion is element wise addition operation. The fused features are then pushed into next layer of RGB feature extractor branch and also form the output P2. Fusion is shown in Figure 34. Concurrent Spatial and Channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’(scSE) attention block is applied on the detection architecture. The scSE blocks are applied on P2, P3, P4 and P5 feature maps extracted from feature extractor backbone.

Experiment 2

In experiment 1, first RGB and Radar data are fused and then attention is applied on output from P2 to P5 but in experiment 2 number of attention blocks are reduced to one. This one attention block is now directly applied on output feature map of Radar feature extractor branch which is before RGB and Radar feature fusion. Fusion location is similar to experiment 1 and fusion operation used is element-wise addition. Feature extractor used on Radar input is shown in Figure 33. Architecture for this experiment is presented in Figure 35.

Experiment 3

In this experiment no ResNet block is applied on Radar input rather it is passed through maxpool to bring it to the size(height and width) equivalent to the size of second stage output of RGB feature extractor. The two are then fused together using element wise addition operation. Output of this branch move to next layer of ResNet block and form P2 as shown in Figure 36.

Evaluation of Single-Level Feature Fusion Experiments

Results corresponding to the above mentioned three experiments of single-level feature fusion are shown in Table 14. All the three versions of single-level feature fusion performed quite close to each other. However, the third experiment is shown in bold yield the best

Figure 35: Experiment 2: Single-level feature fusion(Radar+RGB).

Figure 36: Experiment 3: Single-level feature fusion(Radar+RGB).

results with a gain of approximately 0.7 and 0.3% AP and 0.9 and 0.3% AR in comparison to the other two experiments.

Another observation is about the number of trainable parameters. The first two experiments use ResNet block in Radar feature extraction, whereas the third experiment use max-pooling layer. ResNet block increase the number of trainable parameters with slight performance gain in a few cases. In the third experiment, it is replaced by a simple max-pooling layer, which reduce the number of trainable parameters from 42,301,877 to 42,070,197. Hence the single-level feature fusion shown in Figure has less number of parameters and perform better in comparison to the other two variations.

5.1.2 Multi-Level Feature Fusion

In this set of experiments, Radar data and RGB camera images are fused at multiple levels of feature extractor. The idea behind multi level fusion is to test the method presented in work [Nobis 19]. This set of experiments are also conducted on BIRANet with input size as 1024×1024 . Fusion operation used is element-wise addition and feature extractor used for RGB feature extraction is ResNet50.

Experiment 1

In this experiment also, feature level fusion is performed at multiple stage. Instead of applying ResNet block at first on input Radar data, max-pooling layers are applied to bring it to the size of second stage output of RGB feature extractor. Both of the feature maps are then fused using element wise addition operation. Same process is iterated three times for further three more feature level fusions. Configuration of this experiment is shown in Figure 37.

Figure 37: Experiment 1: Multiple level feature fusion(Radar+RGB).

Experiment 2

In this experiment Radar features are fused at multiple level in feature extractor network as shown in Figure 38. First level fusion between R2 and the second stage output of RGB feature extractor, where R2 is the output of ResNet block applied on input feature map similar to experiment 1 of section 5.1.1. Output of this ResNet block is then maxpooled and scaled to half size and fused with third stage output of the RGB feature extractor. Same process is followed two more times to fuse R4 and R5 with the fourth and fifth stage output of RGB feature extractor network.

Figure 38: Experiment 2: Multiple level feature fusion(Radar+RGB).

Experiment 3

This experiment add two level attention to the architecture of experiment 1. Attention blocks are applied at first and last level of feature extractor as shown in Figure 39. For all level fusion, element-wise addition operation is performed and attention type is scSE.

Figure 39: Experiment 3: Multiple level feature fusion(Radar+RGB).

Experiment 4

In this experiment Radar feature extractor branch contains one ResNet block and feature fusion is performed at all level. However, scSE attention blocks are applied on R2 and R5 Radar feature map. Architectural configuration for this experiment is shown in Figure 40.

Figure 40: Experiment 4: Multiple level feature fusion(Radar+RGB).

Evaluation of Multi-Level Feature Fusion Experiments

Among the experimented four variations of multi-level feature fusion, the configuration experimented in experiment 3 provide best results. Architecture configurations of third experiment is shown in Figure 39, where Radar and RGB features are fused at 4 different levels and two of them are attentive fusions. Results corresponding to all four experiments conducted under multi-level feature fusion are presented in Table 14. Among 4 experiments, best result is highlighted in bold.

5.1.3 Custom Attention

Experiments are conducted with different type of attention methods on proposed object detection network. In section 4.4.3 custom Concurrent Spatial and Channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’ attention block is proposed. The custom scSE attention block is tested on architecture presented in experiment 3 of multi-level feature fusion as a replacement of scSE. Results of this experiment is shown in Table 14. It is clear from the resulting precision and recall values that the custom attention add no benefit to our network instead show a drop of approximate 1.2% in both average precision and average recall.

5.1.4 Mixed Fusion Operation

Till now we are using element wise addition operation for fusing two modality features. As mentioned in section 2.4, there are other fusion operations available. Concatenation fusion operation increase number of parameters and also not good in performance. We experimented with multiplication operation as feature fusion method. Two different architectures are tried with combinations of addition and multiplication fusion operations.

Experiment 1

First architecture is similar to the one experimented in previous section but with different fusion operation. Element wise addition operation is used to fuse R2 and RGB feature map. However, element wise multiplication operation is performed to fuse rest of the Radar feature map R3, R4, R5. Note that attention used in this network is custom Concurrent Spatial and Channel ‘Squeeze & Excitation’(scSE).

Experiment 2

In second variation, type of attention block is changed. Instead of custom scSE this network use scSE attention block. All other configurations are kept same as specified above in experiment 1.

Evaluation of Mixed Fusion Operation Experiments

Results of the two experiments under this section are shown in Table 14. It is clear from the result that feature fusion using element-wise addition operation and scSE attention block provide better performance.

Method	AP	AP50	AP75	AP85	AP(s)	AP(m)	AP(l)	AR	AR(s)	AR(m)	AR(l)
Single-Level Feature Fusion	72.1	88.2	83.9	66.6	52.9	70	75.8	75	55.6	72.9	78.7
	72.5	88.2	83.9	68.3	52.5	70.7	76.1	75.5	54.7	73.8	79.1
	72.8	88.9	84.7	66.5	53.2	70.8	77.6	75.9	56	73.8	79.7
Multi-Level Feature Fusion	72.5	88.2	84.1	68	51.1	71.2	76.6	75.5	54	74.2	79.5
	71.6	87.7	83.3	65.9	51.2	69.9	75.6	74.5	53.6	72.8	78.5
	73.1	89.2	84.8	66.9	52.6	71	77.5	76	55.5	74	80
	72.3	88.5	83.1	67.2	52.3	70.6	76	75.4	55.1	73.7	79.1
Custom Attention	71.8	88.4	83.2	65.9	53	69.6	75.6	74.8	55.3	72.5	78.6
Mixed Fusion Operations	70.1	87.6	82.5	61.9	51.1	68	73.9	73.3	54.1	71.2	77
	71.4	87.5	83.6	65.3	53.5	69.5	74.8	74.4	56.1	72.5	77.2

Table 14: Experiment Result of Single-Level Feature Fusion, Multi-Level Feature Fusion, Custom Attention and Mixed Fusion Operations Experiments.

Comparative Evaluation of Four Fusion Methods

Among the four categories of fusions, as shown in Table 14, the two highlighted results of single-level and multi-level feature fusion performed best. On comparison of the best performing configurations of single-level and multi-level feature fusion, it is observed that both the networks have almost equivalent quantitative results.

The best performing single-level fusion network has 42,070,197 number of parameters; however, the best performing network of multi-level fusion has 45,430,965 number of parameters. Since, mentioned single-level fusion has significantly less number of parameters with equivalent performance, this makes it the best configuration among all experimented single-level and multi-level fusion configurations. All upcoming experiments are conducted on top of this configuration.

5.1.5 Feature Extractor

Feature extraction is an important step that allows us to represent the image as accurately as possible. There is a large number of feature extractors available, but finding suitable feature extractors for specific problems and architecture is a tedious experimental task. In this work, multiple feature extractors are tried before finalizing the best one.

Feature Extractor	Parameters
VGG16	32,582,517
VGG19	37,897,333
ResNet50	42,070,197
ResNet101	61,140,661
DenseNet-121	25,245,493

Table 15: Number of parameter in experimented feature extractors.

A comparison of the number of parameters in each experimented feature extractor is given in Table 15. VGG16 and VGG19 have a vast number of parameters due to the fully connected layers, which are excluded here in the experiments; hence the number of parameters is less than the parameter count of the full network. DenseNet and EfficientNet perform better on Image Net classification task as compare to ResNet50. These two networks are good feature extractors with comparatively fewer parameters; hence experiments are conducted to test there performance on the addressed problem statement.

All feature extractor experiments are conducted on BIRANet and input image of size 1024×1024 . The performance of the experimented feature extractors are shown in Table 16. VGG16 and VGG19 performed much lower than the ResNet50 feature extractor. DenseNet-121 performed better than VGG16 and VGG19 but 3% lower AP and approximately 4% lower AR in comparison to ResNet50. Experiments are also conducted on ResNet101. Not only ResNet101 increase the number of network parameters, but the detection performance is low in comparison to that of ResNet50. Also, it is difficult to train the network on a single 12GB GPU, and training time is too high. So clearly, for the proposed configuration, ResNet50 works best as an RGB camera image feature extractor.

Feature Extractor	AP	AP50	AP75	AP85	AP(s)	AP(m)	AP(l)	AR	AR(s)	AR(m)	AR(l)
VGG16	54.7	76.9	67.6	34.9	32	51.2	63.4	58.4	35.2	54.9	67.2
VGG19	65.7	84.2	77.3	56.7	45.8	63	71.2	69	48.6	66.4	74.4
ResNet50	72.8	88.9	84.7	66.5	53.2	70.8	77.6	75.9	56	73.8	79.7
ResNet101	65.8	85	77.5	54.3	43.9	63.3	72.5	70.1	47.4	67.8	76.3
DenseNet121	69	86.7	81.4	62.6	50.3	67.2	72.5	71.9	48.6	66.4	74.4

Table 16: Comparison of BIRANet on different Feature Extractors Experiments.

5.1.6 Loss Hyperparameters

While combining different loss, 3 hyper parameters λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 are used for classification, regression and anchor loss respectively. In order to find appropriate values for these hyperparameters several experiments are conducted. Few of the hyperparameters values are shown in Table 17.

Config. No.	λ_1	λ_2	λ_3
1	1	1	0.1
2	0.1	0.2	0.1
3	0.2	0.1	0.1
4	0.2	0.2	0.1

Table 17: Loss Hyperparameters.

All three hyperparameter configurations are tested on BIRANet, and the image size used for training and evaluation is 1024×1024 . ResNet50 is used as a feature extractor backbone for RGB camera images. The results of the three experiments conducted are presented in Table 18.

Config	AP	AP50	AP75	AP85	AP(s)	AP(m)	AP(l)	AR	AR(s)	AR(m)	AR(l)
Config 1	71.7	88.7	83.4	66	51	69.9	75.8	74.6	53.7	72.7	78.9
Config 2	72.8	88.9	84.7	66.5	53.2	70.8	77.6	75.9	56	73.8	79.7
Config 3	72	88.6	83.7	66.4	52.4	70	76.1	75.1	55.1	73.1	79.3
Config 4	71.3	88.4	83.1	64.6	52	69.4	75.4	74.5	55.3	72.7	78.2

Table 18: Comparison of BIRANet on different Loss Hyperparameters.

Results of the hyperparameter configurations show that the BIRANet yields the best results on "Config 2", where regression loss is weighted twice in comparison to the classification loss. The results of the three configurations are close, but the network performed better on the second hyperparameter configuration. Results of BIRANet with the second configuration are recorded approximately 1 to 2% higher in all precision and recall subcategories.

5.1.7 Depthwise Separable Convolution

In this experiment, the standard convolution operation is replaced by depthwise separable convolution, which is explained in section 2.2. Generally, Depthwise separable convolution reduce the number of parameters in the network to a large extent and keep the performance still competitive. However, the performance of the network can differ according to the overall architecture, data, and task. Proposed networks are experimented with separable convolution layers, and the results are presented in Table 19. In both the experiments, pre-trained ResNet50 is used as a feature extractor backbone for camera images, and the input image size is kept as 1024×1024 .

Network	AP	AP50	AP75	AP85	AP(s)	AP(m)	AP(l)	AR	AR(s)	AR(m)	AR(l)
RANet	65.8	81.9	75.8	59.2	41.9	64.5	71.5	68.8	44.1	67.6	74.6
BIRANet	65.3	80.9	75.9	59.6	44.6	68.5	67.3	68.5	47.2	71.7	70.2

Table 19: Comparison of BIRANet and RANet with Depthwise Separable Convolution layers.

When the proposed networks have experimented with the depthwise separable convolution layers instead of standard convolution layers, the number of network parameters reduced from 42,070,197 to 38,940,853. However, with depthwise separable convolution performance of BIRANet as well as the performance of RANet decreased. The performance drop for RANet is approximately 3% in AP as well as AR. Whereas, for BIRANet, it is approximately

6%, which is double in comparison to RANet. So depthwise separable convolution may decrease the number of network parameters, but the drop in performance suggest that the standard convolution layers are a better option for the proposed network.

5.1.8 Best Performing Configuration

Best performing configuration obtained from all of the above-described experiments is, the single-level fusion with scSE attention, ResNet50 as feature extractor with standard convolutional layers and hyperparameters λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 as 0.1, 0.2, 0.1. All the mentioned parts of the best configurations are highlighted in their corresponding experiment result tables. From the next section, networks with this best performing configuration are evaluated on a variety of evaluation criteria.

5.1.9 Evaluation on High and Low-Resolution Images

High-resolution cameras are expensive and are not affordable for every vehicle. So it is beneficial if the object detection task can be performed on low-resolution cameras with reasonable accuracy. For this reason, the performance of the proposed fused network is tested on both low and high-resolution images. Proposed networks are trained and evaluated mainly on two resolution images, which are 1024×1024 and 512×512 .

Network	AP	AP50	AP75	AP85	AP(s)	AP(m)	AP(l)	AR	AR(s)	AR(m)	AR(l)
Image Size 512×512											
RANet	65.3	82.9	76.3	56.5	42.8	62.9	70.8	68.3	46.2	66.1	73.6
BIRANet	64.7	82.1	75.1	57.4	41	62.6	70.4	72	49.8	69.5	77.2
Image Size 1024×1024											
RANet	69	83.9	80.1	64.4	44.8	67.8	73.3	71.9	47.3	70.9	76.2
BIRANet	72.8	88.9	84.7	66.5	53.2	70.8	77.6	75.9	56	73.8	79.7

Table 20: Comparison of RANet and BIRANet on Low and High Resolution Images.

According to the quantitative comparison results in Table 20, RANet show a gain of approximately 4% of AP and AR when trained and tested on high-resolution input images as compare to the low-resolution images. When RANet switches to high-resolution input, the object detection performance improves with a significant margin. Specifically, there is an increment of approximately 8% in AP over 85% IOU, which is the detection measure of maximum IOU or overlap with ground truth. Another observation between the two resolution results is that the performance of BIRANet improved significantly for small-sized objects in comparison to medium and large size objects.

Better features help in gathering and learning the content of the image. Since the features of the images are more evident in high-resolution images, the evaluations show better performance on high-resolution images in comparison to low-resolution images. Better features of high-resolution and radar point-based anchors help in getting a more accurate bounding box of the objects. On increasing the resolution performance, overall precision is better, but AP85 is significant because it is the measurement with the highest overlap.

Also, resolution impacts the performance of small objects the most because small objects have comparatively fewer features that networks can learn. When image resolution is reduced to half, these fewer features become further less and difficult for the network to learn. This is the reason behind high improvement in small size object detection

results of BIRANet with the increase in resolution. RANet also show improvement in small-sized object detection. However, the improvement is comparatively less because of the reason that the sensor data do not have radar points corresponding to each object. Also, small-sized objects have very small areas; hence in comparison to objects of larger size, they have less probability to reflect rays of radar sensors.

Qualitative comparison of the effect of image resolution on the detection accuracy is presented in following Table 21 and 22.

Sample Image from NuScenes Evaluation Set.

Detection Results on 512×512 size Images.

Detection Results on 1024×1024 size Images.

Table 21: Qualitative comparison of low and high resolution images effect on detection results of RANet.

time is reduced by 55% as shown in Table 23. To summarize, on low-resolution images, both proposed networks show a performance drop of approximately 4% with two times faster inference.

Image Resolution	Inference Time
512×512	0.08
1024×1024	0.18

Table 23: Inference time on Low and High Resolution Images.

5.1.10 Performance comparison of Proposed Network with FFPN

In this section, both proposed networks BIRANet and RANet are evaluated on NuScenes evaluation set without any augmented noise. The results are compared with FFPN, which is considered as a base object detection network in the presented work. FFPN works on only RGB camera images, RANet, and BIRANet works on both RGB camera images and Radar sensor data. RANet does not utilize all features of the image, but only those who come under anchors generated based on radar sensor data; hence RANet majorly depends on radar modality. A quantitative comparison of the performance of the three networks is presented in Table 24 and Table 25. Results are compared on low-resolution images of size 512×512 and high-resolution images of size 1024×1024 .

In the case of evaluation on low-resolution images, the proposed network RANet, performed with almost equivalent to FFPN. There are low-performance numbers in a few categories, but most of the differences are negligible. This performance indicates that even with the limited number of radar point-based anchors, RANet is able to perform equivalent to FFPN, which utilizes anchors over the entire image. This is because radar point-based anchors provide efficient coverage of a large amount of objects in the image. On high-resolution images, overall AP and AR of RANet are lower than that of FFPN by approximately 1%, which is because RANet can detect the object only if there are corresponding radar points. So in comparison to vision modality based FFPN detection network, even if the resolution is high, the performance of RANet can improve to a limit. The performance differences in individual categories are minute.

On both high and low-resolution images, BIRANet outperform FFPN in all categories and show an increment of approximately 3% in both AR and AP. A possible reason behind the performance of BIRANet is that BIRANet utilize both vision and radar modalities. Vision modality help in detecting objects with good features, and radar modality help in locating objects in areas where there are radar points corresponding to the objects, but the features are not good enough for a vision-based modality to detect them.

Interestingly, independent of image resolution, both BIRANet and RANet show an increase of approximately 4 to 8% in AP85. This improvement indicates that the objects detected by the proposed network overlap with the ground truth object more precisely. Adding radar modality is helping in localizing objects more accurately. Performance under AP85 show further increase for BIRANet because of the proposed target generation method. Best of Two-RPN target generation method help in setting targets with higher IOU with respect to ground truth, which in turn help network in learning object’s localization more precisely with high IOU.

The performance of the three networks can also be evaluated qualitatively based on a few of the detection results presented in Figure 41 and 42.

Figure 41: Qualitative comparison of FFPN, BIRANet and RANet on NuScenes evaluation set1.

Figure 42: Qualitative comparison of FFPN, BIRANet and RANet on NuScenes evaluation set1.

From qualitative comparison, it is found that BIRANet is able to detect objects which are highly blurred and occluded, which align with the quantitative results. For example, in the first example image, FFPN detected a bike and two cars. RANet detected a bike, two cars, and a person standing behind the bike under the street light. Whereas, BIRANet detect two cars, a bike, a person standing behind the bike, and a person sitting on the bike.

5.1.11 Evaluate Robustness against Noise

A network is robust if it can perform efficiently, even in worse conditions. In the autonomous driving environment, most commonly, existing object detectors fail when images are extremely noisy or distorted. Extra noise is added to the evaluation images to test the robustness of the networks. Note that noise is added only to the evaluation set images, and networks are not trained on these noisy images. In order to investigate the robustness of the networks against noise, FFPN, RANet, and BIRANet are evaluated on NuScenes evaluation dataset along with the three augmented noisy evaluation set described in section 4.1.3. Evaluation is done on low as well as high-resolution images to test the robustness in both cases. Quantitative comparison of the evaluation results from the three networks is shown in Table 24 and 25.

When networks are evaluated on four evaluation set, their performance drop with the rise of noise in evaluation images. This behavior is the same for all three networks, FFPN, BIRANet, and RANet. However, as the number of noise increases, the drop in performance of FFPN is high in comparison to the drop in performance of the other two networks. On low-resolution evaluation set 2 where the amount is noise small, the drop in performance is

the same for all three networks. However, on high-resolution images, RANet and BIRANet show a smaller drop with a difference in range 0.1 to 0.3% in comparison to that of FFPN. This difference in performance on high-resolution can be from the fact that a small amount of extra noise distorts the features of low-resolution images harshly, and it is difficult for vision-based networks to detect objects with distorted features. However, in the case of high-resolution images, features are less distorted, and they might not be good enough for a vision-based network(FFPN) to detect but proposed networks(RANet and BIRANet) boost these weak features to a level that the resulting features of some of the objects are good enough for detection.

Network	AP	AP50	AP75	AP85	AP(s)	AP(m)	AP(l)	AR	AR(s)	AR(m)	AR(l)
Evaluation Set 1: With No Additional Noise.											
FFPN(RGB)	65.4	87	76.8	50.2	44.6	63	69.9	68.9	48.4	66.5	73.6
RANet(Radar)	64.7	82.1	75.1	57.4	41	62.6	70.4	67.5	44.1	65.5	72.9
BIRANet(Radar+RGB)	68.7	87.6	79.7	58.2	45.9	65.9	74.2	72	49.8	69.5	77.2
Evaluation Set 2											
FFPN(RGB)	63.7	85.7	75	47.9	40.4	60.8	68.9	67.6	45.2	64.7	72.8
RANet(Radar)	63	81.4	73.3	53.5	37.4	60.5	68.6	65.9	40.6	63.6	71.3
BIRANet(Radar+RGB)	67.4	87.4	77.7	56.2	42.7	64	73.8	70.7	46.8	67.5	76.8
Evaluation Set 3											
FFPN(RGB)	56.8	81.4	66.6	37.3	52.2	54.7	62.5	61.1	36.3	58.9	67
RANet(Radar)	58.3	78	67.6	45.5	33.5	55.5	63.7	61.2	37.2	58.2	66.7
BIRANet(Radar+RGB)	63	85.4	72.1	48.2	38	59.1	70.5	66.4	42.6	62.5	73.7
Evaluation Set 4											
FFPN(RGB)	46.4	66.7	53.7	29.4	31.5	43	50.5	49.3	33.7	45.7	53.4
RANet(Radar)	46.3	63.8	53.6	34.4	27.7	42.1	52.5	48.9	30.1	44.3	54.9
BIRANet(Radar+RGB)	50.4	68.7	59	37.8	32.7	46.3	54.8	53.3	35.3	48.9	57.7

Table 24: Comparison of detection results on 512×512 image size.

Network	AP	AP50	AP75	AP85	AP(s)	AP(m)	AP(l)	AR	AR(s)	AR(m)	AR(l)
Evaluation Set 1: With No Additional Noise.											
FFPN(RGB)	69.7	88.2	82	60.9	50.3	68	73.1	73	53.2	71.3	76.4
RANet(Radar)	69	83.9	80.1	64.4	44.8	67.8	73.3	71.9	47.3	70.9	76.2
BIRANet(Radar+RGB)	72.8	88.9	84.7	66.5	53.2	70.8	77.6	75.9	56	73.8	79.7
Evaluation Set 2											
FFPN(RGB)	68.9	88.1	81.7	59	49.7	67.3	72.2	72.1	52.4	70.6	75.3
RANet(Radar)	68.3	83.3	79.1	62.6	45	66.9	73	71.3	47.1	70	75.9
BIRANet(Radar+RGB)	72.4	88.9	84.3	65.9	51	70.8	77.3	75.4	53.5	73.8	79.5
Evaluation Set 3											
FFPN(RGB)	57	80.5	69	38.2	33.4	55.6	62.4	60.5	35.6	59.3	65.5
RANet(Radar)	58.2	76.5	70	45.2	32.7	55.5	65.7	61.2	34.3	58.4	68.9
BIRANet(Radar+RGB)	62.3	82.1	75.1	47.5	37.1	59.2	69.5	65.3	39.3	62.8	72.1
Evaluation Set 4											
FFPN(RGB)	47.3	64.8	54.9	34.8	37	44.4	49.6	49.8	39.3	46.7	51.9
RANet(Radar)	48	62	56.4	38.8	33.6	44.4	52.4	50.3	35.2	46.4	54.8
BIRANet(Radar+RGB)	51.7	67.4	60.4	41.5	39.7	48.1	54.7	54.2	41.5	50.3	57

Table 25: Comparison of detection results on 1024×1024 image size.

On evaluation set 3 and evaluation set 4, where high and extreme noise is added to the evaluation images, the drop in performance of FFPN is always higher than that of RANet and BIRANet. This observation is the same for both low and high-resolution images. High robustness of the proposed networks RANet and BIRANet on additional noise can be explained by the fact that these networks use radar modality, and radar sensors are not sensitive to the noise. When the input images are highly noisy, the features are distorted, and vision-based detection performance shows a high drop in performance. However, if the

detection network is only based on radar sensor data, noise should not have any impact on detection results. Proposed networks are based on a combination of radar and vision modalities. Due to distorted features, there is a drop in the detection performance of vision branch, but at the same time performance of radar modality remains unimpaired. Hence, with the addition of extra noise, the overall drop in performance of the proposed network is less as compared to the vision-based detection network(FFPN).

Another observation is that on the evaluation set 3 and 4, the drop in performance is more on high-resolution images and less on low-resolution images, which indicate that the networks are more robust on low-resolution images. The possible reason behind this behavior can be that on networks, low-resolution images tend to learn high level because small ones are weak, and the additional noise does not much impact high-level features. However, on high-resolution images, networks can learn minute features as well, which also leads them to better performance. When high noise is added to the high-resolution images, these minute features are extensively distorted; hence networks show a high drop in performance.

For the qualitative comparison, detection results of the three networks on augmented evaluation datasets 2, 3, and 4 are shown in the following Figures from 43 to 48.

Figure 43: FFPN, BIRANet and RANet detection on NuScenes evaluation set 2.

Figure 44: FFPN, BIRANet and RANet detection on NuScenes evaluation set 2.

Figure 45: FFPN, BIRANet and RANet detection on NuScenes evaluation set 3.

Figure 46: FFPN, BIRANet and RANet detection on NuScenes evaluation set 3.

Figure 47: FFPN, BIRANet and RANet detection on NuScenes evaluation set 4.

Figure 48: FFPN, BIRANet and RANet detection on NuScenes evaluation set 4.

5.1.12 Evaluation on Radar Sensed Objects

Radar fusion networks should also focus on objects which are addressed by Radar sensor data or in simpler words objects for which there are corresponding Radar points present. Fusing Radar sensor data and RGB camera images can not give any further improvements

on objects whose features are already clearly visible in the image and are also the part of ground truth. Instead, Radar fusion can help in detecting objects which either have distorted features or are not part of the ground truth, but there are radar points corresponding to those objects in the scene. Hence, radar data cannot help in improving the results if there are no reflected points for the objects in the scenes. So in order to test the benefits from the radar fusion, objects for which there is no radar point in the sensor data are removed from the ground truth. Visualization of the ground truth refinement based on radar points is shown in Figure 49.

Figure 49: Radar point based ground truth refinement.

On analysis, it is found that in the evaluation dataset, 77.78% of ground truth objects have corresponding radar points. Since external weather conditions do not impact radar sensor data, it remains the same, even in the noisy evaluation sets described in section 4.1.3. All networks are evaluated on NuScenes evaluation set 1, which contains no extra noise and on the noisy evaluation set 4. All evaluated networks are trained on the image size of 1024×1024 , and evaluation results are shown in Table 26.

Network	Eval Set1	Eval Set4
FFPN	93.4	75.12
RANet	93.11	77.48
BIRANet	94.15	79.48

Table 26: Radar pointed object detection on NuScenes evaluation set1 and evaluation set 4.

Results on the evaluation set 1 show that the percent of objects detected by FFPN and RANet are almost the same. Whereas, this is higher for BIRANet by approximately one percent. The difference in the percentage of detection increase with the addition of noise to the evaluation images. As shown in results on the evaluation set 4, RANet detection is better than FFPN by 2%, and BIRANet is better by 4%.

With the addition of noise, RGB image features degrade, which causes a decrease in detection performance. However, if the detection network partly relies on another modality that is unaffected by noise, then the network shows less drop in performance. Since both RANet and BIRANet partly rely on radar sensor data, which is insensitive to noise, the drop in performance with added noise is comparatively less. Among RANet and BIRANet, the drop is even less for BIRANet because of the reason that this network use

the combined benefits from vision and radar modality whereas, RANet is limited access to vision modality due to radar point-based anchors.

5.2 Inference Time

All three networks, FFPN, RANet, and BIRANet, experience the same inference time. For high-resolution images of size 1024×1024 , inference time is 0.18 second per image, and for low-resolution images of size 512×512 , it is 0.08 second per image as shown in Table 23.. Proposed networks fuse radar, and vision modalities, show improvement in detection results without any increase in inference time.

5.3 Inference on RRLab dataset

FFPN, RANet and BIRANet are trained on NuScenes dataset. Below are few inference examples on RRLAB dataset (Figure 50). Also a qualitative comparison of detection by these networks is shown in Figure 51 and 52.

Figure 50: Inferences on RRLAB Dataset.

(a) Ground Truth 1

(b) FFPN Detection 1

(c) RANet Detection 1

(d) BIRANet Detection 1

(e) Ground Truth 2

(f) FFPN Detection 2

(g) RANet Detection 2

(h) BIRANet Detection 2

Figure 51: FFPN, BIRANet and RANet detection on RRLAB Dataset.

Figure 52: FFPN, BIRANet and RANet detection on RRLAB Dataset.

5.4 Result Summarization

Two types of fusion called feature level and data level fusion is performed on radar sensor data and RGB camera images. Feature level fusion utilize the location as well as distance property of the radar data points. Whereas, data level fusion offer a way towards radar point-based anchoring technique. Experiments are conducted on multiple levels of feature fusion but the best results are recorded with single-level fusion.

Two architectures named RANet and BIRANet are proposed based on mentioned fusion methods, along with attention and best of two target generation methods described in implementation section. Both types of fusion contribute to better detection results. Multiple feature extractors are tested but ResNet50 gave best results. Image resolution affect the performance of both networks. Multiple types of attention are experimented with various locations in the network, but scSE attention when applied on radar feature map before feature fusion yield best results. Attention mechanism create more focus on radar point location and reduce the focus on other locations comparatively. This in turn boost the activation on radar point locations even in fused feature map. So, if the vision-based features of an object are weak but there are corresponding radar points from radar sensor data, the overall activation of that location is going to be high and this can lead to better detection results.

Detection on high-resolution images gave better precision and recall results as compared to that on low-resolution images. This is due to better features provided by high-resolution

images in comparison to low-resolution images. FFPN is based on vision detection method, RANet is majorly based on radar sensor data and BIRANet is based on best combination of radar and vision modality. RANet performed almost equivalent to the base network FFPN whereas, BIRANet outperform FFPN in all experiments. This observation is true for both high and low-resolution images. BIRANet show an improvement of approximately 3% over FFPN both in precision and recall. Since, BIRANet use both radar and vision modality for detection, it is able to detect objects with good features as well as objects which have weak features such as objects at far distance or objects distorted due to some kind of noise.

Both BIRANet and RANet gave better detection with high IOU as measured by AP85 category. The rise in AP85 is 4-7% by RANet and 6-8% by BIRANet on low and high-resolution images, respectively. Better values of AP85 by RANet and BIRANet is due to radar point based anchors and proposed best of two target generation method.

Even with augmented noise in evaluation set images, the performance of both RANet and BIRANet remains the same in comparison to FFPN. When networks are evaluated on extremely noisy images, the drop in performance is high for FFPN in comparison to the other two. Reason behind this behaviour is due to the fact that radar sensor data is robust against noise. Hence detection networks which are fully or partly depend on radar modality will not show any drop in performance contribution due to radar data based detection, leading to less drop in overall performance of the network.

Networks are also tested specifically to those objects corresponding to which there are radar points in radar sensor data. AS observed everywhere, in this experiment also FFPN and RANet performed almost similar and BIRANet outperformed both of them. Evaluation results show that when noise is added to the evaluation images, networks fused with radar data detected more objects in comparison to FFPN, which work on RGB camera images only. The percentage of objects detected by FFPN is 2% less in comparison to that of RANet and 4% less in comparison to BIRANet. The behavior of RANet and BIRANet on noisy images prove the robustness of the networks against noise. BIRANet not only show robustness towards noise but also improve the detection results with no inference or training time overhead.

5.5 Comparison with existing Radar Fusion Methods

In this section, the results of the proposed network BIRANet are compared with the existing detection methods, which use fusion of two modalities; radar and RGB camera images. All networks considered for comparison are trained and evaluated on the NuScenes dataset.

The first comparison is done with RRPN [Nabati 19]. As the input image resolution is not mentioned in work, it is considered to be NuScenes original image resolution, which is 900x1600. Performance of RRPN is compared with the performance of RANet and BIRANet on input images of resolution 1024×1024 . The results of the two methods are shown in Table 27. From the comparison, it is clear that both proposed networks show a tremendous improvement over RRPN. RANet show an improvement of 26% AP and 23.3% AR whereas, BIRANet outperform RRPN by 29.8% AP and 27.3% AR. Similar improvements can be seen in all subcategories of AP and AR measurements.

Network	AP	AP50	AP75	AR	AR(s)	AR(m)	AR(l)
RRPN	43	64.9	48.5	48.6	4	41.2	58.2
RANet	69	83.9	80.1	71.9	47.3	70.9	76.2
BIRANet	72.8	88.9	84.7	75.9	56	73.8	79.7

Table 27: Comparison of BIRANet and RANet with RRPN.

The second comparison is with RVNet, a network based on YOLO framework with two SSD feature extractor branch as explained in related work. Input image resolution in RVNet is 416×416 which is compared with the proposed networks on low-resolution input. RVNet show average precision of 56 percent which is very low in comparison to mean average precision(average of average precision) of proposed networks.

Another comparison is made with CameraRadarFusion Net (CRF-Net). The input image size used in CRF-Net is 360×640 , so the comparison is done with RANet and BIRANet on 512×512 as this is the lowest resolution results available. In this retinanet based object detection method, a total of 55.99% mean average precision is recorded.

Network	mAP(%)
RVNet	56
CRF-Net	55.99
RANet	69
BIRANet	72.8

Table 28: Comparison of BIRANet and RANet with RVNet and CRF-Net.

Despite of using different image resolution and detection architectures, Both RVNet and CRF-Net yield approximately equal mAP. Proposed networks outperform the performance of RVNet and CRF-Net. RANet show 13% better mAP and BIRANet show approximately 16% better mAP in comparison to RVNet and CRF-Net.

5.6 Detection failure

As explained in the implementation, RANet works on anchors generated corresponding to the radar points. RANet detection is dependent on radar modality. Also, radar sensor data should be good enough to point the reflective objects. If radar data points are not good, detection on RANet are going to be bad.

Occluded object detection is a well-known problem in the object detection task. Proposed networks fail to detect objects where there is high occlusion. Interestingly, this problem is not faced in every occluded scene. On further analysis, it is observed that networks are able to detect highly occluded objects if they belong to different categories. However, detection fail if occluded objects belong to the same category. For example, in the sub-figure (D) of Figure 53 shown below, a person and motorcycle are slightly occluded, and both objects are detected correctly. Even with high occlusion between motorcycle and person, as shown in sub-figure (B), both RANet and BIRANet efficiently detected the two objects. Whereas,

Figure 53: Detection Failure on Ocluded Objects.

in the same scene, networks are not able to detect all instances of the category 'Person' when there is high occlusion, as shown in sub-figure (B). There are 5 instances of category 'person' in the sub-figure (C), and proposed networks are able to detect only three of them. Few other examples of such cases of detection failure are shown in Figure 54 below.

Figure 54: More examples of Detection Failure on Occluded Objects.

6 Conclusion

In this section, the methods, reasoning and results of the presented work is summarised concisely. Further to this, possible future improvements and related research areas are discussed.

6.1 Discussion and summary

Dozens of research works are present in autonomous vehicle domain, but very few of them deal with radar and vision modalities using DL techniques. Perhaps the main hurdle behind this is the public availability of suitable datasets. In the vision domain, there is a large number of excellent datasets available for public research. However, to our knowledge, only one dataset is made publically available, which includes synchronized radar and vision data for autonomous driving scenarios. Before the release of NuScenes, multiple works were present on these radar and vision modalities. However, all of them were limited to private organizations, few of them explored DL techniques too, but the scope was again limited. With the release of NuScenes, a research area of multi-sensor DL based object detection and tracking in the autonomous driving area is triggered. Since then, there are few works specific to object detection task on radar and vision modalities, which are described shortly in related work.

FFPN is considered as a base network for the proposed detection networks, which is a vision based two-stage object detection network. The presented work further explores object detection tasks with ideas for improvement on the existing detection method. In this work, two multi-model object detection networks are proposed, named as RANet and BIRANet. These networks fuse radar and RGB camera images using feature and data level fusion methods. An RPN based on radar points is used as a replacement of a standard region proposal used in FFPN. In radar point-based RPN, anchors are generated in the surrounding of radar point coordinate location. RANet primarily use radar point based anchor method for anchor generation. However, BIRANet use this in combination with the standard FFPN's anchoring schemes to get the benefit from the best of the two methods. Adding radar point based anchors validate the localization of objects in the scene. Also, it help in boosting the activation of areas where there are objects in the scenes but the features are not good enough to identify the objects by vision based modality. The attention mechanism is used further to boost up the good features creating focus at radar point locations.

For any DL based solution, representative data is at utmost priority. NuScenes dataset cover a large variety of driving scenarios along with various weather and lighting conditions. This dataset includes crowded as well as sparse scenes with few objects. For training and evaluation NuScenes dataset is used. NuScenes dataset contains high-resolution images which might not be affordable for all type of vehicles, so the networks are trained and tested on low-resolution images as well. On evaluation, it is found that proposed networks provide good detection results even on low-resolution images. This observation show that, proposed networks can benefit autonomous vehicles that cannot afford multiple expensive high-resolution cameras. High-resolution cameras can be used at a prime location where the risk rate is high, and low-resolution cameras along with radar sensors can be placed at low risk location. This can resolve the problem of cost and provide excellent output. Also, on low resolution images the inference time is reduced by 55% which makes the inference

two times faster in comparison to the inference on high-resolution images. Benefit of faster inference on low-resolution images can be utilized in area where speed of the detection results is more important and slight drop in performance quality is acceptable.

It is possible that the outdoor condition in a driving scenario can become worse than those captured in NuScenes dataset. In such scenarios, how is the network going to perform? How robust can the network be against the noise? To find answers to these questions, networks are trained on the standard NuScenes dataset and evaluated on three sets of augmented noisy evaluation datasets. These evaluation datasets cover shallow noise conditions to extremely high augmented noisy conditions. Evaluations on the described dataset measure the robustness of the network against noise. In order to carefully evaluate the improvement by the addition of radar modality to the object detection network, another evaluation is based on radar pointed objects only. Evaluation results prove the improvements and robustness of the proposed networks due to added radar modality, which remain unimpaired with increase in noise. The performance gain is achieved without any additional inference time, and memory consumption is reduced in comparison to base network FFPN. Evaluations are described both qualitatively and quantitatively for better understanding. Proposed methods also outperform the existing radar and vision fusion based detection networks on the NuScenes dataset by a significant gain in precision and recall.

6.2 Future Work

This section covers the possible areas of improvements in the research domain of object detection in autonomous driving. As mentioned in previous chapter, the proposed network and most of the object detection networks face the problem of occlusion. It would be great to work further on the proposed network to tackle this problem using heuristic methods. RPN used in the proposed network is the fusion of basic FFPN's RPN with radar point-based anchors. After FFPN, there are several types of improved RPNs are proposed in different works. The recent state of art RPN method is cascade RPN [Vu 19] which use deformable adaptive convolution operation. Since proposed radar and vision fusion show an improvement over a single modality based two-stage detection method, it is assumed that the same is applicable for two-stage networks with state of the art RPN method. However, it would be interesting to implement the fusion network along cascade RPN and explore further with new ways of region proposal generations.

Presented work is limited to 2d object detection, and the dataset used for training and evaluation is from sensors on the front and back of the driving vehicle. In future work, even left and right side sensors can be used to create an entire 3D scene, and the work can be extended to real-time 3D object detection.

In real-time applications, it is essential to have minimal latency in prediction. Proposed fusion methods are fast enough for real-time applications, but the latency can be reduced further by reducing model size. Pruning is one of the immensely researched methods for model compression, which helps in identifying and removing irrelevant parameters of the network. Pruning not only makes the network faster but can sometimes enhance the performance as well.

Object tracking is another area that can be explored in the future as an extension of the proposed fusion network. Velocity component of radar sensor data can also be used

in determining relative directions and distance between moving objects. Also, decision level fusion would be interesting for performance comparison or can be experimented in combination with the feature level fusion and data level fusion techniques.

References

- [Bombini 06] L. Bombini, P. Cerri, P. Medici, G. Alessandretti, “Radar-vision fusion for vehicle detection”, in *Proceedings of International Workshop on Intelligent Transportation*. 2006, pp. 65–70.
- [Caesar 19] H. Caesar, V. Bankiti, A. H. Lang, S. Vora, V. E. Liong, Q. Xu, A. Krishnan, Y. Pan, G. Baldan, O. Beijbom, “nuScenes: A multimodal dataset for autonomous driving”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1903.11027*, 2019.
- [Chadwick 19] S. Chadwick, W. Maddetn, P. Newman, “Distant vehicle detection using radar and vision”, in *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, IEEE. 2019, pp. 8311–8317.
- [Chavez-Garcia 12] R. O. Chavez-Garcia, J. Burlet, T.-D. Vu, O. Aycard, “Frontal object perception using radar and mono-vision”, in *2012 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium*, IEEE. 2012, pp. 159–164.
- [Cheng 95] Y. Cheng, “Mean shift, mode seeking, and clustering”, *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, vol. 17, no. 8, pp. 790–799, 1995.
- [Chollet 17] F. Chollet, “Xception: Deep learning with depthwise separable convolutions”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2017, pp. 1251–1258.
- [Deng 09] J. Deng, W. Dong, R. Socher, L.-J. Li, K. Li, L. Fei-Fei, “Imagenet: A large-scale hierarchical image database”, in *2009 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, Ieee. 2009, pp. 248–255.
- [Duan 16] J. Duan, L. Ren, L. Li, D. Liu, “Moving objects detection in evidential occupancy grids using laser radar”, in *2016 8th International Conference on Intelligent Human-Machine Systems and Cybernetics (IHMSC)*, vol. 2, IEEE. 2016, pp. 73–76.
- [Eigen 13] D. Eigen, M. Ranzato, I. Sutskever, “Learning factored representations in a deep mixture of experts”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1312.4314*, 2013.
- [Feng 20] D. Feng, C. Haase-Schütz, L. Rosenbaum, H. Hertlein, C. Glaeser, F. Timm, W. Wiesbeck, K. Dietmayer, “Deep multi-modal object detection and semantic segmentation for autonomous driving: Datasets, methods, and challenges”, *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2020.
- [fractal 19] fractal, “Mask R-CNN Unmasked”, <https://medium.com/@fractaldle/mask-r-cnn-unmasked-c029aa2f1296>, 2019.
- [Frossard 17] D. Frossard, “VGG in TensorFlow”, *VGG in TensorFlow*. Davi Frossard, 2017.
- [Gao 17] H. Gao, “Faster R-CNN Explained”, *Diambil kembali dari: https://medium.com/@smallfishbigsea/faster-r-cnn-explained-864d4fb7e3f8*, 2017.
- [Gidaris 16] S. Gidaris, N. Komodakis, “Attend refine repeat: Active box proposal generation via in-out localization”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1606.04446*, 2016.

- [Girshick 14] R. Girshick, J. Donahue, T. Darrell, J. Malik, “Rich feature hierarchies for accurate object detection and semantic segmentation”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2014, pp. 580–587.
- [Girshick 15] R. Girshick, “Fast r-cnn”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*. 2015, pp. 1440–1448.
- [He 16] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, J. Sun, “Deep residual learning for image recognition”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2016, pp. 770–778.
- [He 17] K. He, G. Gkioxari, P. Dollár, R. Girshick, “Mask r-cnn”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*. 2017, pp. 2961–2969.
- [Hosang 17] J. Hosang, R. Benenson, B. Schiele, “Learning non-maximum suppression”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2017, pp. 4507–4515.
- [Howard 17] A. G. Howard, M. Zhu, B. Chen, D. Kalenichenko, W. Wang, T. Weyand, M. Andreetto, H. Adam, “Mobilenets: Efficient convolutional neural networks for mobile vision applications”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1704.04861*, 2017.
- [Hu 18] J. Hu, L. Shen, G. Sun, “Squeeze-and-excitation networks”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2018, pp. 7132–7141.
- [Iandola 14] F. Iandola, M. Moskewicz, S. Karayev, R. Girshick, T. Darrell, K. Keutzer, “Densenet: Implementing efficient convnet descriptor pyramids”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1404.1869*, 2014.
- [Ioffe 15] S. Ioffe, C. Szegedy, “Batch normalization: Accelerating deep network training by reducing internal covariate shift”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1502.03167*, 2015.
- [Jacobs 91] R. A. Jacobs, M. I. Jordan, S. J. Nowlan, G. E. Hinton, “Adaptive mixtures of local experts”, *Neural computation*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 79–87, 1991.
- [Jiang 19] Y. Jiang, L. Duan, J. Cheng, Z. Gu, H. Xia, H. Fu, C. Li, J. Liu, “JointRCNN: A Region-based Convolutional Neural Network for Optic Disc and Cup Segmentation”, *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 2019.
- [John 19] V. John, S. Mita, “RVNet: Deep Sensor Fusion of Monocular Camera and Radar for Image-Based Obstacle Detection in Challenging Environments”, in *Pacific-Rim Symposium on Image and Video Technology*, Springer. 2019, pp. 351–364.
- [Kato 02] T. Kato, Y. Ninomiya, I. Masaki, “An obstacle detection method by fusion of radar and motion stereo”, *IEEE transactions on intelligent transportation systems*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 182–188, 2002.
- [Kawasaki 04] N. Kawasaki, U. Kiencke, “Standard platform for sensor fusion on advanced driver assistance system using bayesian network”, in *IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, 2004*, IEEE. 2004, pp. 250–255.

- [Krizhevsky 12] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, G. E. Hinton, “Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks”, in *Advances in neural information processing systems*. 2012, pp. 1097–1105.
- [Lin 14] T.-Y. Lin, M. Maire, S. Belongie, J. Hays, P. Perona, D. Ramanan, P. Dollár, C. L. Zitnick, “Microsoft coco: Common objects in context”, in *European conference on computer vision*, Springer. 2014, pp. 740–755.
- [Lin 17a] T.-Y. Lin, P. Dollár, R. Girshick, K. He, B. Hariharan, S. Belongie, “Feature pyramid networks for object detection”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2017, pp. 2117–2125.
- [Lin 17b] T.-Y. Lin, P. Goyal, R. Girshick, K. He, P. Dollár, “Focal loss for dense object detection”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*. 2017, pp. 2980–2988.
- [Lindeberg 12] T. Lindeberg, “Scale invariant feature transform”, 2012.
- [Liu 05] T.-Y. Liu, Y. Yang, H. Wan, H.-J. Zeng, Z. Chen, W.-Y. Ma, “Support vector machines classification with a very large-scale taxonomy”, *Acm Sigkdd Explorations Newsletter*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 36–43, 2005.
- [Liu 16] W. Liu, D. Anguelov, D. Erhan, C. Szegedy, S. Reed, C.-Y. Fu, A. C. Berg, “Ssd: Single shot multibox detector”, in *European conference on computer vision*, Springer. 2016, pp. 21–37.
- [Long 19] N. Long, K. Wang, R. Cheng, W. Hu, K. Yang, “Unifying obstacle detection, recognition, and fusion based on millimeter wave radar and RGB-depth sensors for the visually impaired”, *Review of Scientific Instruments*, vol. 90, no. 4, p. 044102, 2019.
- [Manjunath 18] A. Manjunath, Y. Liu, B. Henriques, A. Engstle, “Radar based object detection and tracking for autonomous driving”, in *2018 IEEE MTT-S International Conference on Microwaves for Intelligent Mobility (ICMIM)*, IEEE. 2018, pp. 1–4.
- [Mees 16] O. Mees, A. Eitel, W. Burgard, “Choosing smartly: Adaptive multimodal fusion for object detection in changing environments”, in *2016 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, IEEE. 2016, pp. 151–156.
- [Meyer 19] M. Meyer, G. Kusch, “Deep learning based 3d object detection for automotive radar and camera”, in *2019 16th European Radar Conference (EuRAD)*, IEEE. 2019, pp. 133–136.
- [Nabati 19] R. Nabati, H. Qi, “RRPN: Radar Region Proposal Network for Object Detection in Autonomous Vehicles”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.00526*, 2019.
- [Neumann 17] D. Neumann, T. Langner, F. Ulbrich, D. Spitta, D. Goehring, “Online vehicle detection using Haar-like, LBP and HOG feature based image classifiers with stereo vision preselection”, in *2017 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, IEEE. 2017, pp. 773–778.

- [Nobis 19] F. Nobis, M. Geisslinger, M. Weber, J. Betz, M. Lienkamp, “A Deep Learning-based Radar and Camera Sensor Fusion Architecture for Object Detection”, in *2019 Sensor Data Fusion: Trends, Solutions, Applications (SDF)*, IEEE. 2019, pp. 1–7.
- [Redmon 16] J. Redmon, S. Divvala, R. Girshick, A. Farhadi, “You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2016, pp. 779–788.
- [Ren 15] S. Ren, K. He, R. Girshick, J. Sun, “Faster r-cnn: Towards real-time object detection with region proposal networks”, in *Advances in neural information processing systems*. 2015, pp. 91–99.
- [Roy 18] A. G. Roy, N. Navab, C. Wachinger, “Concurrent spatial and channel ‘squeeze & excitation’ in fully convolutional networks”, in *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*, Springer. 2018, pp. 421–429.
- [Sambasivarao 19] K. Sambasivarao, “Non-maximum Suppression (NMS)”, <https://towardsdatascience.com/non-maximum-suppression-nms-93ce178e177c>, 2019.
- [Simonyan 14] K. Simonyan, A. Zisserman, “Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.1556*, 2014.
- [Szegedy 15] C. Szegedy, W. Liu, Y. Jia, P. Sermanet, S. Reed, D. Anguelov, D. Erhan, V. Vanhoucke, A. Rabinovich, “Going deeper with convolutions”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2015, pp. 1–9.
- [Tan 19] M. Tan, Q. V. Le, “Efficientnet: Rethinking model scaling for convolutional neural networks”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1905.11946*, 2019.
- [Valada 17] A. Valada, J. Vertens, A. Dhall, W. Burgard, “Adapnet: Adaptive semantic segmentation in adverse environmental conditions”, in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, IEEE. 2017, pp. 4644–4651.
- [Vu 19] T. Vu, H. Jang, T. X. Pham, C. Yoo, “Cascade RPN: Delving into High-Quality Region Proposal Network with Adaptive Convolution”, in *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*. 2019, pp. 1430–1440.
- [Wang 19] J. Wang, K. Chen, S. Yang, C. C. Loy, D. Lin, “Region proposal by guided anchoring”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. 2019, pp. 2965–2974.
- [Wu 09] S. Wu, S. Decker, P. Chang, T. Camus, J. Eledath, “Collision sensing by stereo vision and radar sensor fusion”, *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 606–614, 2009.
- [Xie 17] S. Xie, R. Girshick, P. Dollár, Z. Tu, K. He, “Aggregated residual transformations for deep neural networks”, in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2017, pp. 1492–1500.
- [Zhang 19a] G. Zhang, H. Li, F. Wenger, “Object Detection and 3D Estimation via an FMCW Radar Using a Fully Convolutional Network”, *arXiv preprint arXiv:1902.05394*, 2019.

[Zhang 19b] R. Zhang, S. Cao, “Extending Reliability of mmWave Radar Tracking and Detection via Fusion With Camera”, *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 137065–137079, 2019.